

Review Article

Ternary Transition Metal Oxides for Electrochemical Energy Storage: Synthesis, Advantages, Design Strategies, and Future Prospects

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Ternary transition metal oxides (TTMOs) have emerged as a new class of electrode materials for high-performance energy storage systems, particularly supercapacitors (SCs) and hybrid battery-capacitor devices. This comprehensive review aims to comprehensively survey recent advances in the design, synthesis, and analysis of TTMOs-based nanostructures for SC electrodes. It begins by outlining the key concepts related to charge storage mechanisms in SC electrodes, electric double-layer (EDL) capacitance, pseudocapacitive (PC), and battery-type (BT) behavior, followed by a clarification of device configurations, including symmetric SC (SSC), asymmetric SC (ASC), and hybrid SC (HSC) devices. This review then examines the fabrication strategies for TTMOs, emphasizing the impact of synthetic approaches on material morphology, crystallinity, and electrochemical performance. Special attention is given to the structure-property relationships that govern ion transport and charge storage dynamics in these materials. The influence of morphological features, including dimensionality, porosity, and hierarchical architecture, on electrochemical behavior is critically analyzed. A comparative evaluation of electrochemical matrices across various TTMO electrodes is presented, highlighting key performance and challenges. Ultimately, the review highlights emerging trends, current limitations, and future research directions that are poised to accelerate the development of next-generation TTMO materials for advanced energy storage technologies.

Keywords: electrode materials; nanostructures; supercapacitors; synthetic methods; ternary transition metal oxides

1. Introduction

As the social economy continues to advance rapidly, global energy demand is intensifying. Fossil fuel reserves, comprising coal, oil, and natural gas, are finite and nonrenewable, and their combustion contributes significantly to environmental pollution, raising serious concerns about long-term sustainability and ecological impact [1, 2]. In response, renewable energy generated from sources such as wind, tidal, and solar power has emerged as a viable alternative to meet the growing energy

needs driven by population growth and technological progress. These options are not only efficient and cost-effective but also offer a more sustainable path forward [3, 4]. However, the inherent intermittency, instability, and spatial constraints of renewable energy technologies highlight the pressing need for advanced energy storage systems to ensure grid reliability and a stable power supply [5, 6]. Alongside these developments, the increasing adoption of hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) and portable electronic devices (PEDs) has further intensified the demand for high-performance energy storage solutions [7].

Meeting this demand presents significant challenges, particularly in terms of enhancing energy density, power density, and long-term stability [8, 9]. Thus, the development of efficient, sustainable, and robust electrical energy storage (EES) systems is paramount.

Recent advances in materials science and device engineering have led to the development of next-generation EES technologies, demonstrating strong potential for enhancing performance, reliability, and scalability [10, 11]. Supercapacitors (SCs) are an innovative energy storage solution within the domain of emerging EES systems [12, 13]. They bridge the gap between traditional capacitors and batteries by offering a higher energy density than conventional capacitors while delivering power output that surpasses that of batteries [14–16]. Additionally, SCs exhibit interesting application potential due to their superior charge–discharge capabilities, enhanced safety features, eco-friendliness, customizable operating parameters, and extended operational lifespan compared to traditional batteries and fuel cells [17–19]. SC devices possess a remarkable versatility, making them suitable for a wide range of applications. These applications include, but are not limited to, hybrid vehicles, electronic devices, military operations, aircraft, uninterruptible power supplies, smart grids, and forklifts [20, 21]. The efficiency of electrochemical energy storage systems is significantly governed by the properties of the electrode materials [22–24]. Therefore, pursuing research and development focused on innovative electrode materials with superior SC performance characteristics is essential to meet the demands of actual applications [25–27].

Nanotechnology has advanced materials science by enabling the synthesis and engineering of innovative materials and nanostructures, allowing for new manipulation of matter at the nanoscale [28–30]. Particularly, transition metal oxides (TMOs) with nanoarchitectures have gained attention for their diverse properties, which are vital for enhancing high-performance energy storage devices compared to traditional carbon-based materials and conducting polymers [31–33]. Compounds made of transition metal cations and oxygen anions exhibit diverse structures and electronic configurations, enhancing their redox activities and versatility in various applications. TMOs have a high theoretical specific capacitance, making them promising for use in SCs [34]. However, their low electrical conductivity limits performance, highlighting the need for improvements in this area [35, 36]. Utilizing binary metal compounds in electrocapacitive materials provides advantages over single metal compounds by facilitating more Faradaic redox reactions on the electrodes, thus enhancing performance and efficiency [37–39]. In relation to this idea, it is attractive to explore if an increased number of Faradaic redox reactions could be produced, leading to greater specific capacitances when additional transition metals are involved in the electrocapacitive material [40]. This prompts an important interrogation: could the integration of additional transition metals improve Faradaic redox reactions and, in turn, enhance the electrochemical performance of electrode materials? [41].

Building on the insights above, it is proposed that trimetallic/ternary TMOs (TTMOs) can serve as superior alternatives to bimetallic compounds for use as electrodes, thereby

improving electrochemical properties. The enhanced performance of these materials can be attributed to a synergistic effect, which leverages the benefits of a greater variety of metal ions [11, 42]. The integration of various cations to form TTMO, along with the capability to tailor their stoichiometric and nonstoichiometric compositions, presents significant opportunities for manipulating their electrochemical properties [43, 44]. This class of TTMO materials has garnered significant attention owing to their intriguing properties, including (i) the presence of synergistic effects, (ii) the ability to accommodate varying metal cation ratios, (iii) intricate chemical compositions that contribute to superior reversible capacities, (iv) enhanced electrical conductivity driven by the low activation energy facilitating electron transfer among cations, (v) increased electrochemical stability, (vi) environmentally sustainable attributes, and (vii) superior electrochemical synergy when compared to binary and unitary counterparts [45–48]. Moreover, the presence of diverse metallic species in TTMO materials enhances the density of electroactive centers, each of which exhibits multiple redox states, facilitating Faradaic redox reactions. This enables operation at elevated current densities, ultimately leading to improved device performance [49]. Furthermore, the integration of inexpensive metal species into TTMO not only reduces the overall expenses but also enhances the safety of the electrode system. Additionally, this approach may have a significant impact on the electrochemical charge storage capabilities [50–53]. Moreover, TTMOs are classified into two groups: poly- and monocrystalline. The polycrystalline category consists of a mixture of different individual metal oxides. In contrast, monocrystalline TTMOs primarily include some types that exhibit no significant changes in crystal structure. When compared to polycrystalline TTMOs, the monocrystalline ones demonstrate superior morphology and electrochemical performance due to the beneficial synergistic interactions among multiple metal species within the monocrystalline framework [54].

This review provides a comprehensive overview of recent advancements in the design and development of TTMOs-based electrode materials for SC applications. It begins with an outline of the summarizing essential concepts related to charge-storage mechanisms in SC electrodes, distinguishing among electric double layer (EDL) materials, pseudocapacitive (PC) materials, and battery-type (BT) materials. Differences between device configurations, namely symmetric SC (SSC), asymmetric SC (ASC), and hybrid SC (HSC), are also clarified. The main discussion is structured around several key areas: first, the fabrication methods for TTMOs are examined, with emphasis on how synthesis routes influence material characteristics. Next, the relationship between structure and electrochemical performance is explored, highlighting how morphological features and material architecture impact energy storage behavior. In this context, the charge storage mechanisms specific to TTMOs are analyzed in detail. Finally, the electrochemical performance metrics of reported TTMO-based electrodes are critically evaluated. Drawing from these insights, the review concludes by outlining future directions and challenges that could guide the development of next-generation TTMO materials for high-performance energy storage systems.

2. SC and Its Classifications

SCs, commonly referred to as electrochemical capacitors, are advanced energy storage devices that operate by storing and releasing energy through the electrostatic separation of charges as well as Faradaic processes [55, 56]. Electrochemical SCs have clearly outpaced conventional dielectric SCs, thanks to their superior speed and lucrativeness [57]. However, the efficacy of an SC is primarily influenced by the characteristics of its electrode material [58–60]. The electroactive materials exploited in SC systems can be classified into three distinct categories based on their charge storage mechanisms. These categories include (i) EDL, (ii) PC, and (iii) BT materials [5, 61–63]. The EDLs store energy through the accumulation of charges at the electrolyte-electrode interface, characterized as a non-Faradaic process that doesn't involve any electrochemical reactions. Carbon-based materials are typically employed for this purpose due to their favorable properties. In contrast, PC materials utilize fast and reversible near-surface or surface-confined Faradaic reactions as their energy storage mechanism. These materials include TMOs such as MnO_2 and RuO_2 , as well as various conducting polymers. Meanwhile, BT materials store energy through diffusion-controlled Faradaic reactions that involve the intercalation and deintercalation of ionic species into or from electroactive compounds, commonly exemplified by nickel and cobalt-based hydroxides and oxides [64–67]. Each type of electrode material has its own set of strengths and weaknesses, particularly when considering specific applications. EDLs demonstrate excellent cycle stability, attributed to the absence of redox reactions, allowing their charging and discharging processes to achieve high reversibility. Nonetheless, the energy density of EDLs remains inferior to that of PCs and BTs, limiting their wider implementation in energy storage applications [68, 69]. Conversely, the advantage of PCs compared to EDLs lies in their ability to provide high capacitance and energy density. This is primarily due to the efficient charge storage mechanisms associated with Faradaic redox reactions [70–72]. Meanwhile, BTs offer superior energy density relative to EDLs and demonstrate enhanced cycle stability when contrasted with PCs [73]. To overcome this limitation, SC devices often integrate various electrode materials, utilizing a positrode (Faradaic as energy source) and a negatrode (non-Faradaic as power source) within a coherent hierarchical framework. This configuration optimizes performance by leveraging the distinct electrochemical properties of each electrode type [74, 75]. This approach optimally utilizes the varied potential windows of the two electrodes, enabling the single cell system to achieve a maximum operational voltage. As a result, there is a significant enhancement in specific capacitance and a noteworthy improvement in energy density. This is accomplished while preserving the inherent advantages of SCs, such as rapid charge–discharge capabilities and a long cycle life [1, 76]. Particularly, SC devices can be classified into three main types: (a) SSCs, (b) ASCs, and (c) HSCs, each with unique energy storage mechanisms and electrode materials. They are: (a) In symmetric SCs, both the positrode and negatrode are constructed from identical capacitive materials. These materials can be EDL or PC types [77–79]. They provide rapid

charge and discharge cycles, offering high power density but limited energy density. (b) ASCs: these feature different materials for each electrode, often combining EDL with Faradaic materials, such as PCs (e.g., MnO_2) [80–82]. This design enhances energy density while maintaining fast charge capabilities. (c) HSCs: HSCs blend EDL and BT characteristics by utilizing various electrode types, thereby achieving both high energy and power densities [10, 83–85]. As a result, HSCs effectively integrate the advantageous properties of both BT and EDL SC systems. They provide the high energy density characteristic of BT materials while simultaneously achieving the extended cycle life and superior power density associated with EDLs. Consequently, it is crucial to engineer advanced hierarchical electrode materials that exhibit synergistic properties and enhanced electrochemical performance, as these characteristics are essential for achieving optimal outcomes in energy storage systems [86, 87]. Figure 1 illustrates an overview of various strategies for integrating different electrode materials with their associated energy storage systems. This design highlights potential approaches for merging these components to enhance energy storage solutions [88, 89].

3. Synthetic Methods and Functional Properties of TTMO Nanostructures

This section provides an overview of the various synthesis approaches employed in the fabrication of TTMO for SC applications. Numerous researchers worldwide are actively pursuing scalable and advanced TTMO electrode materials characterized by diverse nanostructures of varying dimensions, coupled with strong electrochemical performance. However, developing a standardized and cost-effective synthesis method for these materials remains a significant challenge. The synthesis method selected for a material has a significant impact on its physicochemical and electrochemical properties. These factors collectively play a crucial role in determining the overall performance of SCs. According to the findings presented in relevant works, numerous studies highlight that while a variety of techniques have been used for the synthesis of TTMO nanomaterials, the hydrothermal methods are the most commonly employed. These methods are favored because they enable superior control over critical factors, such as crystallinity, size, and shape, which are essential for optimizing the properties of nanostructures. Other synthesis strategies, including solvothermal, coprecipitation, electrodeposition, microwave-assisted synthesis, sol–gel, and chemical bath deposition (CBD), have been employed in the preparation of TTMOs for SC applications. The key factors that significantly influence the final properties of these materials include the reaction duration and heat-treatment temperature, as well as the choice of surfactants, among others. Understanding and optimizing these factors are essential for enhancing the performance of TTMOs in energy storage solutions. A schematic representation of various synthesis techniques, along with their typical characteristics, is illustrated in Figure 2. Additionally, Table 1 summarizes the methodological approaches for synthesizing TTMO nanoarchitecture materials and their corresponding electrochemical performance, as outlined in the relevant literature.

FIGURE 1: (A) A proposed framework for integrating the properties of electrode materials in SC devices and (B) schematic representations illustrating various potential merging approaches for electrode materials of energy storage systems.

FIGURE 2: A schematic overview of the diverse synthesis methods with their key features for TTMOs.

3.1. Hydrothermal and Solvothermal. The synthesis of TTMO materials can be efficiently achieved through a hydrothermal or solvothermal method. The solvothermal process utilizes an organic solvent as the reaction medium, providing a nonaqueous alternative to traditional aqueous solvents used in hydrothermal. These approaches refer to the process of fabricating nanoarchitecture materials utilizing superheated solvents within high-pressure autoclaves. Under conditions of elevated

temperature and pressure, reactants exhibit enhanced solubility and reactivity, facilitating the formation of particles with nanometer-scale dimensions. Several reaction parameters significantly influence the synthesis outcome and play a critical role in determining the features of the final materials. These factors include the type and concentration of chemicals used, the choice of solvent, the presence of stabilizing agents, as well as the temperature and duration of the process. Each of these

TABLE 1: A comprehensive overview of various TTMOs employed as electrode materials with diverse synthesis and morphological approaches, along with their electrochemical performance metrics in SCs.

Electrode materials	Synthesis technique	Morphology	Electrolyte	Capacitance (or) capacity	Energy density	Power density	Stability (cycle)	Ref.
Zn _{0.5} Cu _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Flower	2 M KOH	1776 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	122.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	91.0% (10,000)	[31]
Fe-Mn-Zn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	1673.4 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	75.3 Wh kg ⁻¹	649.9 W kg ⁻¹	88.7% (10,000)	[32]
Ni-Co-Mo-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	1837.7 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	67.1% (1600)	[35]
CoMnFeO ₄	Hydrothermal and sol-gel	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	770 and 150 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[36]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Chemical bath deposition	Nanosheets	1 M KOH	715.1 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	36.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	320.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.5% (6000)	[37]
Co-Mn-Cu-O/Ag ₂ O	Sputtering	Microflower	1 M KOH	2136.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mV s ⁻¹	98.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	3000.0 W kg ⁻¹	88.0% (4000)	[38]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Electrodeposition	Nanosheet	1 M KOH	1800.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	39.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	1300.0 W kg ⁻¹	90.0% (3000)	[39]
NiCoMoO	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	1 M KOH	2.94 F cm ⁻² at 1.63 mAh cm ⁻²	22.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	3.5 W kg ⁻¹	—	[40]
NiCo _{2-x} MnxO ₄ @Ni-MOF-1	Hydrothermal	Hybrid of Nanosheet/ Nanoflower/Nanorod/ Nanosphere	2 M KOH	3543.5 F g ⁻¹ at 6 mA g ⁻¹	33.8 Wh kg ⁻¹	750.0 W kg ⁻¹	106.0% (5000)	[41]
Ni-Co-Mo-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	1696.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	89.3% (20,000)	[42]
MnZnCo ₂ O ₄	Co-precipitation	Nanosphere	2 M KOH	589.9 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[43]
Fe-Ni-Co-O	Co-precipitation	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	532.7 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[44]
NiCoMoO _x	Solvothermal	Yolk-shell hollow sphere	3 M KOH	1125.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	44.7 Wh kg ⁻¹	804.0 W kg ⁻¹	93.0% (5000)	[45]
Fe-Co-Cu-O/S	Sol-gel	Spherical bead	6 M KOH	3899.7 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	80.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	450.0 W kg ⁻¹	92.2% (10,000)	[46]
CNT@GdCoBiO	Hydrothermal	Plate-like hybrid	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	1197.0 F g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	52.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	500.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.0% (10,000)	[47]
Cu-Mn-Ni-O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	2 M KOH	790.6 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[48]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	6 M KOH	2082.21 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	37.89 Wh kg ⁻¹	749.8 W kg ⁻¹	90.0% (1000)	[49]
Mg-Ni-Co-O	Electrodeposition	Nanoglass	3 M KOH	846.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	31.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	393.0 W kg ⁻¹	95.0% (4000)	[50]
Ni-Zn-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Microflower	2 M KOH	776 F g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	44.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	880.0 W kg ⁻¹	96.5% (1000)	[51]
Ni _{0.5} Cu _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Microflower	3 M KOH	367.4 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	53.1 Wh kg ⁻¹	700.3 W kg ⁻¹	99.6% (5000)	[52]
MnNiCoO/RGO	Co-precipitation	Nanoparticles	6 M KOH	646.1 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	35.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	699.9 W kg ⁻¹	77.2% (10,000)	[53]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Microsphere	6 M KOH	766 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	41.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	850.0 W kg ⁻¹	90.0% (20,000)	[54]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	1 M KOH	2481.8 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	35.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	150.1 W kg ⁻¹	94.0% (3000)	[90]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Microflower	2 M KOH	259.8 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	55.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	761.5 W kg ⁻¹	89.0% (5000)	[91]
Ni _{3-x} Co _x V ₂ O ₈	Hydrothermal	Oval-shaped particle	3 M KOH	391.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	25.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	937.5 W kg ⁻¹	85.9% (10,000)	[92]
Ru-NiCo ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Microflower	2 M KOH	1526.8 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[93]
Zn-Mn-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	3 M KOH	1330.0 C g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	—	—	81.0% (5000)	[94]
Sulfur-doped Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	6 M KOH	2919.6 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	72.9 Wh kg ⁻¹	825.0 W kg ⁻¹	89.3% (5000)	[95]
MnNiCo ₄ @MnO ₂	Hydrothermal	Nanowire/nanosheet	6 M KOH	1931.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.8 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[96]
NiCoMoO ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	3 M KOH	354.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	16.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	725.0 W kg ⁻¹	—	[97]
ZnCo ₃ O ₄ -NiO	Solvothermal	Nanosheet	2 M KOH	1573.7 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	322.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	1680.0 W kg ⁻¹	63.3% (6000)	[98]
P-doped Ni _{0.5} Cu _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄	Solvothermal	Yolk-shell hollow sphere	6 M KOH	1570.2 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mA cm ⁻²	118.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	78.0% (5000)	[99]
(CNT)/P-(Ni/Mn) Co ₂ O ₄ @NGQD	Hydrothermal	Core-shell nanospheres	6 M KOH	2172.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	94.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	86.4% (10,000)	[100]
AC/NiCoSnO ₄	Co-precipitation	Nanoparticle	0.1 M K ₃ [Fe(CN) ₆] + 3 M KOH	478.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	9.66 Wh kg ⁻¹	471.3 W kg ⁻¹	78.0% (5000)	[101]

TABLE 1: Continued.

Electrode materials	Synthesis technique	Morphology	Electrolyte	Capacitance (or) capacity	Energy density	Power density	Stability (cycle)	Ref.
Co ₃ O ₄ -MnO ₂ -NiO	Electrodeposition	Nanotube	1 M KOH	2525.3 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[102]
Co ₂ NiV ₂ O ₇ @rGO	Electrodeposition	Nanosheet	1 M KOH	701.08 F g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[103]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Microwave irradiation	Nanoflake	6 M KOH/ 0.01 M K ₃ Fe (CN) ₆	2536.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mA cm ⁻²	41.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	1400.0 W kg ⁻¹	73.5% (5000)	[104]
Mn _{0.5} Ni _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄ /C	Sol-gel	Nanosheet	2 M KOH	91.2 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[105]
CuCoFe ₂ O ₄				221.1 F g ⁻¹	7.90 Wh kg ⁻¹	1711.9 W kg ⁻¹	—	
NiCoFe ₂ O ₄				60.0 F g ⁻¹	4.79 Wh kg ⁻¹	1426.2 W kg ⁻¹	—	
NiCuFe ₂ O ₄				16.9 F g ⁻¹	4.62 Wh kg ⁻¹	1001.9 W kg ⁻¹	—	
				at 10 mV s ⁻¹				
PPy/rGO/NiCoFe ₂ O ₄	Sol-gel	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	222.5 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[107]
Cu-Fe-Co-O	Chemical bath deposition	Nanoneedle	3 M KOH	737.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	48.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	796.0 W kg ⁻¹	95% (5000)	[108]
AlNiCo-O	Hydrothermal	Microflower	6 M KOH	1008.5 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	63.3 Wh kg ⁻¹	881.4 W kg ⁻¹	84.3% (5000)	[109]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	1728.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[110]
CuCo ₂ V ₂ O ₈	Self-templating	Hollow spheres	3 M KOH	799.8 C g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[111]
NiMnFe ₂ O ₄	Microwave-assisted combustion	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	476.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[112]
NiCoMoO	Hydrothermal	Nanoflower	6 M KOH	1724.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	44.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	824.8 W kg ⁻¹	68.2% (10,000)	[113]
NiCoAl ₂ O	Hydrothermal	Nanowires/nanosheets	6 M KOH	8.22 F cm ⁻² at 1 A g ⁻¹	58.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.3 W kg ⁻¹	75.1% (2000)	[114]
Ni-Co-Cu-O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	2 M KOH	6.54 F cm ⁻² at 3 A g ⁻¹	42.1 Wh kg ⁻¹	374.9 W kg ⁻¹	40.0% (2000)	[115]
Co ₂ Ni ₂ ZnO ₈	Solvothermal	Nanowire	6 M KOH	1115.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	62.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	89.6% (2000)	[116]
Ce-SnFe ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	2 M KOH	1216.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[117]
B-doped Cu-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoneedle	3 M KOH	974.0 C g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	42.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	926.0 W kg ⁻¹	87.0% (8000)	[118]
Mn-doped NiCoFeO ₄	Hydrothermal	Microflower	3 M KOH	500.0 mF cm ⁻² at 5 mA cm ⁻²	60.0 μWh cm ⁻²	2.0 mW cm ⁻²	92.0% (1000)	[119]
V-doped Fe ₂ (MoO ₄) ₃	Hydrothermal	Flower	1.5 g KOH/ 3 g PVA	2157 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	151.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	96.2% (10,000)	[120]
NiCoFeO/PANI	Sol-gel autocombustion	Stacked nanoparticle	0.5 M K ₃ [Fe(CN) ₆]	843.0 F g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[121]
rGO/CoMnFeO ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	380.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[122]
PEDOT-PSS/NMCO	Solvothermal-coprecipitation	Microrods	6 M KOH	1234.5 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[123]
rGO/Ni ₂ nFeO/polyindole	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	320.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.3 A g ⁻¹	16.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	1784.0 W kg ⁻¹	84.0% (2000)	[124]
Zn-Ni-Co-O/PG	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	2 M KOH	502.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.2 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[125]
AgBiMgO-rGO/PANI	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	1770.8 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[126]
Fe-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoflake	1 M KOH	867.0 F g ⁻¹ at 3 A g ⁻¹	40.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	750.0 W kg ⁻¹	99.2% (5000)	[127]
ZnO/Co ₃ O ₄ /NiO	Co-precipitation	Double shell rhombic dodecahedral	2 M KOH	1119.1 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	95.8 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.5% (10,000)	[128]
Zn _{0.5} Cu _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	669.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	55.1 Wh kg ⁻¹	1280.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.9% (10,000)	[129]
Zn-Co-Mo-rGO	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	2 M KOH	1189.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	14.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	750.0 W kg ⁻¹	95.0% (1000)	[130]
NiCoMnO/rGO	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle/nanosheet	3 M KOH	115.0 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	27.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	598.0 W kg ⁻¹	96.0% (2000)	[131]
MnVMo-O	Hydrothermal	Microrod	1 M KOH	814.5 mF cm ⁻² at 3 mA cm ⁻²	0.025 mWh cm ⁻²	1.5 mW cm ⁻²	71.5% (9000)	[132]
Fe-Co-Ni-O/GF	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	1 M KOH	1.34 F cm ⁻² at 0.5 mA cm ⁻²	16.76 μWh cm ⁻²	69.94 μW cm ⁻²	87.5% (8000)	[133]
3DG@Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoblade/nanoparticle	1.06 gr LiClO ₄ in 10 ml	62.5 F g ⁻¹ at 40 mV s ⁻¹	81.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	750.0 W kg ⁻¹	80.0% (1000)	[134]

TABLE 1: Continued.

Electrode materials	Synthesis technique	Morphology	Electrolyte	Capacitance (or) capacity	Energy density	Power density	Stability (cycle)	Ref.
Ni-Co-Mg-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoflake	6 M KOH/PVA	198 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	70.70 Wh kg ⁻¹	360.0 W kg ⁻¹	99.8% (50,000)	[135]
V-doped Zn-Ni-Co-O	Spin and dip coating	Nanosheet	1.77 g KOH KOH/PVA	-	148.0 mWh kg ⁻¹	12.0 km W kg ⁻¹	94.0% (5000)	[136]
Ni _{0.8} Mn _{0.2} Co ₂ O ₄	Deep eutectic solvents (DESS)	Nanoflake	1 M KOH	761.0 mAh g ⁻¹ at 30 mA cm ⁻²	66.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	1519.0 W kg ⁻¹	92.9% (10,000)	[137]
Cu-Zn-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoflake	2 M KOH	215.0 C g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[138]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	1 M KOH	439.12 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mA cm ⁻²	—	—	—	[139]
g-C ₃ N ₄ / ZnO/Fe ₂ O ₃ /SrO ₂ g- C ₃ N ₄ / NiO/Fe ₂ O ₃ /Dy ₂ O ₃	Co-precipitation/sol-gel/ Sonochemical	Nanoparticle	6 M KOH	84,570 mF cm ⁻² at 2 mV s ⁻¹ 30,070 mF cm ⁻² at 2 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[140]
Ni _{0.5} Zn _{0.5} Fe ₂ O ₄ - CNT	Electrospinning	Nanofiber	6 M KOH	833.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	39.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	1000.0 W kg ⁻¹	95.0% (5000)	[141]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoneedle	2 M KOH	1156.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[142]
Co-Mn-Zn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticles	3 M KOH	675.3 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	12.06 Wh kg ⁻¹	324.9 W kg ⁻¹	68.9% (2000)	[143]
CT@Zn/NiMnO-rGO	Wet-chemical reduction	Nanoplate@ nanoribbons	2 M KOH	1404.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.1 A g ⁻¹	121.8 Wh kg ⁻¹	8.03 kW kg ⁻¹	83.3% (10,000)	[144]
MnO ₂ /CuO/ ZnO ₂	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	1 M KOH	869.8 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[145]
Mn _{0.8} Ni _{0.2} Co ₂ O ₄	Solvothermal	Microsphere	6 M KOH	1822.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[146]
SiC supported Bi-Co-Zn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	1 M KOH + 1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	841.1 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	76.3 Wh kg ⁻¹	900.0 W kg ⁻¹	84.2% (10,000)	[147]
Ni-Mn-Fe-O	Electrodeposition	Nanosheet	1 M NaOH	3950.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	94.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	750.0 W kg ⁻¹	75.0% (10,000)	[148]
Ni-Mn-Zn-O	Hydrothermal	Spherical	3 M KOH	1311.0 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	23.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	650.0 W kg ⁻¹	51.8% (20,000)	[149]
Co-Ni-Mn-O	Chemical reduction and oxidation	Nanoparticle/nanosheet	6 M KOH	811.8 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[150]
Fe-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	6 M KOH	2197.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	47.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	375.0 W kg ⁻¹	86.0% (15,000)	[151]
Ni _{0.5} Mn _{0.5} Co ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanoflower	6 M KOH	366.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	20.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	700.0 W kg ⁻¹	82.0% (5000)	[152]
MnNiCo ₂ O ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	2 M EMIMBF ₄ and Na ₂ SO ₄	150.3 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	45.4 Wh kg ⁻¹ 19.9 Wh kg ⁻¹	200.0 W kg ⁻¹ 100.0 W kg ⁻¹	99.4% (10,000) 98.3% (10,000)	[153]
Co-Ni-Mn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	1 M KOH	612.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.5 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[154]
MnNiCoO/GNP	Hydrothermal	Dendrite	6 M KOH	605 mAh g ⁻¹ at 2 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[155]
Mn-Ni-Co-O	Co-precipitation	Honeycomb	6 M KOH	1260.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[156]
Zn-Co-Mo-O	Hydrothermal	Microflower	1 M KOH	384.0 F g ⁻¹ at 60 mA cm ⁻²	—	—	—	[157]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Hydrothermal	Hollow urchin	1 M KOH	208.3 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[158]
Cu-Mn-Zn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	806.8 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	44.3 Wh kg ⁻¹	1299.9 W kg ⁻¹	111.1% (3000)	[159]
NiCoFe ₂ O ₄	Microwave-assisted combustion	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	314.9 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	6.4 Wh kg ⁻¹	1904.7 W kg ⁻¹	94.2% (5000)	[160]
Al-Mn-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	923.1 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	88.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	799.0 W kg ⁻¹	100% (3000)	[161]
Ni _{0.5} Fe _{0.5} Mn ₂ O ₄	Reflux	Hexagonal bipyramid/sheets	3 M KOH	827.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	75.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	1166.0 W kg ⁻¹	73.0% (5000)	[162]
No-Co-Mo-O	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	2 M KOH	1366.0 F g ⁻¹ at 2 A g ⁻¹	46.2 Wh kg ⁻¹	713.0 W kg ⁻¹	89.8% (5000)	[163]
NiFeCo-O		Nanosheet		943.0 F g ⁻¹				
ZnFeCo-O		Nanowire		948.0 F g ⁻¹				
AlFeCo-O		Nanosheet	2 M KOH	464.0 F g ⁻¹				[164]
MgFeCo-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire		313.0 F g ⁻¹				
CuFeCo-O		Nanowire		271.0 F g ⁻¹ at 50 mV s ⁻¹				

TABLE 1: Continued.

Electrode materials	Synthesis technique	Morphology	Electrolyte	Capacitance (or) capacity	Energy density	Power density	Stability (cycle)	Ref.
Cu-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	3 M KOH	2535 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	39.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	450.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.0% (5000)	[165]
Ni-Co-Cu-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	1 M KOH	2.28 F cm ⁻² at 5 mA cm ⁻²	0.69 Wh kg ⁻¹	13.37 W kg ⁻¹	83.2% (10,000)	[166]
Ni-Cu-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	596.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	96.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	841.0 W kg ⁻¹	—	[167]
Mn-Sn-Co-O	Electrodeposition	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	4.15 F cm ⁻² at 1 A g ⁻¹	39.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	800.0 W kg ⁻¹	93.5% (3000)	[168]
CuCoNi _{0.5} O _{4-x}	Hydrothermal	Whisker	3.5 M KOH	3612.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	53.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	805.0 W kg ⁻¹	52.0% (20,000)	[169]
Ti-Mo-Ni-O _x	Anodization	Nanotube	1 M K ₂ SO ₄	0.54 mF cm ⁻² at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[170]
Zn-Ni-Co-O	Solvothermal	Nanosheet	6 M KOH	220.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[171]
Co-Ni-Cu-O	Electrodeposition	Nanosheet	2 M NaOH	188.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	61.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	200.0 W kg ⁻¹	98.0% (5000)	[172]
CuMnCoO ₄	Hydrothermal	Nanoneedle	3 M KOH	1715.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	40.1 Wh kg ⁻¹	799.0 W kg ⁻¹	93.0% (10,000)	[173]
Ni _{0.5} Co _{0.5} MoO _{4-x} H ₂ O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	2 M KOH	665.0 F g ⁻¹ at 5 A g ⁻¹	45.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	815.0 W kg ⁻¹	93.0% (9950)	[174]
Mn-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	6 M KOH	638.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	123.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	264.0 W kg ⁻¹	95.2% (6000)	[175]
SrO/BaO/Al ₂ O ₃	Sol-gel Combustion	Microleaf	0.1 M KOH	97.2 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[176]
Ni-Co-Mo-O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	6 M KOH	441.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	25.6 Wh kg ⁻¹	775.0 W kg ⁻¹	—	[177]
ZnNiCoO/3DG	Hydrothermal	Microsphere	2 M KOH	133.65 μAh cm ⁻² at 10 mV s ⁻¹	8.52 mWh cm ⁻²	1329.44 mW cm ⁻²	119.0% (2000)	[178]
Ni-Co-Sn-O	Pechini	Nanoclay	6 M KOH	328.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[179]
Ni-doped CuMnFeO ₄	Sol-gel auto combustion	Nanoparticle	1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	875.0 F g ⁻¹ at 20 mA cm ⁻²	—	—	—	[180]
Ni-Co-Mo-O		Nanosheet		0.85 F cm ⁻²			40.3% (2500)	
Ni-Co-Zn-O		Nanosheet		1.72 cm ⁻²	0.70 Wh kg ⁻¹	13.4 W kg ⁻¹		
Ni-Co-Cu-O	Hydrothermal	Nanowire	1 M KOH	2.28 cm ⁻²	21.9 Wh kg ⁻¹	3.5 W kg ⁻¹	83.3% (2500)	[181]
Ni-Co-Fe-O		Nanowire		1.63 cm ⁻²				
Ni-Co-Al-O		Nanosheet		1.94 cm ⁻² at 10 mA cm ⁻²				
NiCoFeO ₄	Microwave	Nanorod	6 M KOH	1263.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	9.8 Wh kg ⁻¹	1000.0 W kg ⁻¹	94.0% (4000)	[182]
Mn-Cu-Ni-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoleaf	1 M KOH	754.6 F g ⁻¹ at 5 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[183]
Co-Ni-Fe-O	Electrodeposition	Nanoparticle	2 M NaOH	440.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.25 A g ⁻¹	14.3 Wh kg ⁻¹	500.0 W kg ⁻¹	92.0% (1000)	[184]
Zn-Mn-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoneedle	3 M KOH	849.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	35.5 Wh kg ⁻¹	802.0 W kg ⁻¹	100.0% (7000)	[185]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoneedle	2 M KOH	2023.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mA cm ⁻²	—	—	—	[186]
Cu-Ni-Co-O	Hydrothermal	Nanoflake	3 M KOH	2615.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	51.0 Wh kg ⁻¹	764.0 W kg ⁻¹	97.3% (10,000)	[187]
Ni-Co-Mn-O	Hydrothermal	Nanorod	2 M KOH	500.0 F g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[188]
Eu-ZnCo ₂ O ₄	Sol-gel	Nanoflower	—	1750.0 F g ⁻¹ at 3 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[189]
CoMnNiC ₂ O ₄ nH ₂ O	Co-precipitation	Polyhedron	3 M KOH	990.0 F g ⁻¹ at 0.6 A g ⁻¹	—	—	—	[190]
LaNiFeO	Sol-gel	Cubic granular	2 M KOH	893.0 C g ⁻¹ at 1 A g ⁻¹	67.1 Wh kg ⁻¹	580.1 W kg ⁻¹	90.0% (10,000)	[191]
NiFeCuO	Hydrothermal	Nanoparticle	3 M KOH	546.0 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	—	—	—	[192]
Al-Mn-Zn	Hydrothermal	Nanosheet	3 M KOH	1915.2 F g ⁻¹ at 10 mV s ⁻¹	57.09 Wh kg ⁻¹	1299.9 W kg ⁻¹	81.9% (5000)	[193]

FIGURE 3: Schematic illustration depicting (A) the synthesis process for hierarchical mesoporous ZnCo (ZNCO) electrode materials (Reproduced with permission from [90]. Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society); (B) the synthesis process for 3D hierarchical ZnCo flower-like superstructures (Reproduced with permission from [91]. Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society); (C) the growth mechanism of 3D porous oval $\text{Ni}_{3-x}\text{Co}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_8$ nanostructures (Reproduced with permission from [92]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier); and (D) synthesis strategy of RNCO on NF (Reproduced with permission from [93]. Copyright 2018, Elsevier).

elements intricately contributes to the overall effectiveness and quality of the synthesis. The solvothermal system is highly advantageous for synthesizing nanomaterials, particularly for water-sensitive chemicals.

For instance, Wu et al. [90] introduced a straightforward and environmentally sustainable method for synthesizing three-dimensional (3D) nickel foam (NF)-supported hierarchical mesoporous Zn–Ni–Co oxide (ZNCO) nanowire arrays (Figure 3A). The study further investigates their physical and electrochemical properties, emphasizing their potential as a

binder-free electrode material for SCs. Initially, during the hydrothermal process (130°C for 5 h), the raw materials react to form the precursor for hierarchical mesoporous ZNCO nanowires. This precursor undergoes calcination in air at 350°C for 2 h to produce the final product. The application of ZNCO as an electrode material for SCs was explored for the first time, demonstrating outstanding electrochemical performance characteristics [90]. Acharya et al. [91] described a simple method involving a hydrolysis reagent-assisted hydrothermal process, followed by calcination, to fabricate a

distinctive 3D hierarchically nanostructured ZNCO. It was directly synthesized on NF, serving as a binder-free electrode suitable for high-performance HSCs. In this study, hydrolysis reagents, specifically urea and hexamethylenetetramine (HMT), are considered crucial in synthesizing the desired 3D hierarchically nanostructured ZNCO. The effects of various hydrolysis reagents, including urea, a urea/HMT combination, and HMT alone, were thoroughly examined. The findings indicated that the exclusive use of HMT as a hydrolysis reagent led to the formation of a nanosheet structure, whereas the use of urea resulted in a nanowire architecture. Notably, the unique combination of urea and HMT as hydrolysis agents resulted in the formation of distinctive 3D hierarchical nanowire-incorporated nanosheet hybrids. These hybrids comprise 2D nanosheets that were anchored with a 3D nanowire architecture of ZNCO (Figure 3B) [91]. Merum et al. [92] introduced a facile approach for synthesizing porous 3D oval cobalt-doped nickel vanadate nanoparticles (NPs) via a hydrothermal method (Figure 3C). When Co was employed as a dopant in the Ni lattice sites, the resultant particles in the sample tended to aggregate. This aggregation leads to a morphological transition, where the initial cuboidal structure evolves into a 3D oval shape. The agglomeration step was predominantly driven by electrostatic interactions among ions, resulting in alterations to the sample's morphology. The electrostatic attraction resulting from the smaller ionic radius of Ni in conjunction with oxygen ions is enhanced in the presence of Co ions occupying the nickel positions, suggesting that the potential for agglomeration is increased. A porous 3D oval-shaped Co-doped nickel vanadate is generated as a consequence of particle growth through the Ostwald ripening process. The resulting interconnected NPs facilitate a shorter transportation pathway for both electrons/ions [92]. Yang et al. [93] have reported the incorporation of ruthenium into nickel–cobaltite using a hydrothermal process followed by annealing. This method facilitates the transformation of the precursor into $\text{Ru}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4$ (RNCO), applied on an NF (Figure 3D). The incorporation of Ru into the NCO significantly enhanced the material's conductivity, increased the number of active chemical reaction sites, and substantially improved the capacitive performance of the electrodes. The improved micro/nanostructure offers an increased specific surface area while effectively reducing the transportation path. The excessive introduction of Ru adversely affected the conductive properties and specific surface area of the RNCO material. These limitations resulted in relatively low capacitance. The assurance of a stable structure contributes significantly to enhanced electrochemical stability [93].

Sahoo et al. [94] prepared ternary Zn–Mn–Co–O (ZMCO) nanoflakes on NF via hydrothermal synthesis followed by a calcination step (Figure 4A). The interconnected network structure, characterized by its porous and sheet-like formation, offered significant advantages in maximizing electrochemically active sites while enhancing mechanical adhesion. The enhanced conductive properties of the TTMO could be significantly attributed to the strong synergy created by the interaction of dissimilar metals. The increased presence of transition metals in ZMCO, in comparison to its binary and mono counterparts, contributes to enhanced redox activity by increasing

the number of redox-active sites. This enhancement significantly improves its PC characteristics [94]. Guo et al. [95] detailed the synthesis of sulfur-doped ZNCOs (S-ZNCOs) by leveraging a synergistic approach that combines heteroatom doping and defect engineering (Figure 4B). This was achieved through a hydrothermal treatment followed by a sulfurization process. Prior to sulfur doping, the ZNCO material exhibits uniformly structured nanoneedle arrays cultivated on NF. The incorporated sulfur atoms into the ZNCO material generated oxygen vacancies, thereby enhancing the electrical conductivity of the electrode material. The impact of sulfur doping on the nanoneedles' surface morphology was notable. When the doping level was either insufficient or too high, the resulting roughness of the nanoneedles was minimal, and in some cases, agglomeration occurred. This observation highlighted the significant impact that the degree of sulfidation had on the electrode's structural properties. The results demonstrated that all sulfur-doped samples participate in the same redox reaction. However, variations in the morphology and microstructure of the electrodes, resulting from differing sulfur doping levels, significantly influenced their electrochemical performance. The S-ZNCO electrode material demonstrated distinct BT electrochemical properties [95]. Saray et al. [96] described a 3D hierarchical mesoporous $\text{MnNiCoO}_4@\text{MnO}_2$ hybrid composite, exhibiting strong adhesion to a CC (Figure 4C). This innovative material served as a self-supported SC electrode and was synthesized using a two-step hydrothermal approach followed by a low-temperature annealing process. The direct synthesis of hierarchical hybrid nanostructure arrays on flexible CC acted as a free-standing electrode. The systematic development of heterostructures presented an opportunity to harness the admirable synergistic properties of multifunctional composite nanostructures. This distinctive nanostructure exhibited several advantages, including an extensive surface area, increased availability of active sites, enhanced infiltration and diffusion characteristics, superior electrical conductivity, and exceptional electrochemical and mechanical stability. The $\text{MnNiCoO}_4@\text{MnO}_2$ nanostructured electrode displayed significantly enhanced PC performance compared to both BTMO and MTMO counterparts [96]. Prabhu et al. [97] synthesized $\text{Ni}_{(1-\alpha)}\text{Co}_{(\alpha)}\text{MoO}_4$ nanorod composites through a hydrothermal method, varying the α parameter at 0, 0.1, 0.3, and 0.5 M to investigate the effects of cobalt content on the material properties (Figure 4D). The physicochemical and electrochemical characteristics of the synthesized materials were significantly influenced by the Ni/Co ratio. When the Ni/Co ratio was equal, the electrode material exhibited exceptional rate capabilities and cycling durability, alongside a noteworthy specific capacity. The observation of redox peaks was substantiated by the battery-like charging characteristics exhibited by all samples [97].

Gourji et al. [45] fabricated a novel type of hollow spheres made from nickel–cobalt–molybdenum oxide (NCMO) through a self-templating method. It consists of two main steps: first, the solvothermal process (200°C for 24 h) of solid NCM-glycerate spheres, and then the oxidation (400°C for 2 h) of these spheres to create nanoporous yolk-shell NiCoMoO_x hollow spheres (NCMO-YSHSs) (Figure 5A). The oxidation

FIGURE 4: Schematic depiction illustrating (A) the synthetic methodology employed for the preparation of ZMCO nanostructure (Reproduced with permission from [94]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier); (B) the synthetic pathway employed for the generation of S-ZNCO nanomaterial (Reproduced with permission from [95]. Copyright 2022, Elsevier); (C) the procedures for the efficient preparation of self-supported mesoporous MnNiCoO₄@MnO₂ core-shell hybrid nanostructures (Reproduced with permission from [96]. Copyright 2016, Elsevier); and (D) the preparation approach of Ni_(1- α)Co_(α)MoO₄ nanorods (Reproduced with permission from [97]. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society).

process facilitates the conversion of NCM-glycerates into NCMO-YSHSs. The oxidative decomposition of organic constituents leads to a decrease in the core size of NCM-glycerates, resulting in an inward contraction of the structure. If the contraction process continues, the core would persist in its inward shrinking, eventually resulting in its detachment from the encompassing outer metal oxide shell. The unique nanostructure of the nanoporous YSHSs enhances electron transport and ion diffusion, ultimately improving the electrode's electrochemical properties [45]. Liu et al. [98] conducted a study in which they synthesized a free-standing ZnCo₂O₄-NiO composite nanosheet array using a solvothermal approach, derived from a ZnCoNi-MOF precursor on NF, followed by a subsequent annealing step in air (Figure 5B). The sample features a nanosheet consisting of a multilayer chip structure. This structure consists of individual, thin nanoplate strips arranged in an orderly manner on NF. Each nanoplate has a thickness of ~120 nm, suggesting that the material exhibits a high level of stability. The ZnCo₂O₄-NiO electrode exhibited a high specific capacity and impressive retention, indicating its superior

electrochemical performance [98]. Liu et al. successfully synthesized uniformly dispersed phosphorus-doped Ni_{0.5}Cu_{0.5}Co₂O₄ (P-NCCO) spheres featuring a yolk-shell hollow structure. This was achieved through a solvothermal method followed by high-temperature phosphating (Figure 5C). The P-NCCO demonstrated a consistently distributed yolk-shell spherical structure, as evidenced by the observed broken notch. The P-doping could enhance both the conductivity and surface activity of the NCCO electrode. As a result, P-NCCO revealed significantly improved electrochemical performance [99]. Liu et al. [100] synthesized a ternary composite film consisting of CNT/P-(NiMn)Co₂O₄@NGQD through meticulous optimization of reaction parameters (Figure 5D). This was crucial for achieving a uniform morphology of the precursor throughout the synthesis process. Modifying the surface with phosphides enabled the incorporation of phosphorus atoms, thereby improving the electrical properties of the materials. This strategy not only enhanced the specific surface area but also augmented the available volume for nitrogen incorporation. These films acted as the active electrode material for SCs, significantly

FIGURE 5: Schematic representation of (A) the fabrication process for nanoporous NCMO-YSHSs (Reproduced with permission from [45]. Copyright 2023, Royal Society of Chemistry); (B) the synthesis pathway for $\text{ZnCo}_2\text{O}_4\text{-NiO}$ nanosheet arrays anchored on NF (Reproduced with permission from [98]. Copyright 2023, Royal Society of Chemistry); (C) the synthesis process for $\text{P-Ni}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4$ spheres (Reproduced with permission from [99]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier); and (D) the synthesis approach of $\text{CNT/P-(NiMn)Co}_2\text{O}_4\text{@NGQD}$ composite thin film (Reproduced with permission from [100]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier).

improving their performance characteristics. The improved electrochemical properties are ascribed to the large specific surface area and abundant active sites present in the $\text{CNT/P-(NiMn)Co}_2\text{O}_4\text{@NGQD}$ films. Additionally, the synergistic interactions between the NGQD and metal ions enhance the kinetics of electron and charge transfer processes [100].

3.2. Co-precipitation. Co-precipitation stands out due to its capability to simultaneously precipitate various materials, allowing for the generation of NPs in one process. This method offers a facile and cost-effective approach compared to other synthesis techniques. This method provides significant flexibility in tailoring the composition and characteristics of NPs. Its importance in NP synthesis is further amplified by its facile implementation and scalability. This process involves combining metal salt solutions with a precipitating agent, resulting in the formation of metal hydroxide precipitates. When these precipitates undergo thermal treatment, they are converted into metal oxides. The co-precipitation method consists of several key stages: nucleation, growth, coarsening, and aggregation. The initial stage, nucleation, focuses on the formation of small NPs, while the subsequent stage, growth, involves variations in size, shape, and properties of these NPs.

Wu et al. [53] successfully synthesized rGO nanosheet-supported Mn-Ni-Co-O (rGO-MNCO) through a facile co-precipitation reaction followed by calcination (Figure 6A).

In the resulting solution, metal ions, specifically Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} , closely interact with the functional groups on the surface of GO, such as $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{COOH}$. As the reaction temperature reaches 90°C , HMT decomposes, leading to an increase in pH. This pH shift facilitates the formation of the Mn-Ni-Co precursor, promoting preferential nucleation on the GO sheets' surface. The abundant hydroxyl and carboxyl groups generated during the hydrolysis of trisodium citrate dihydrate aid in the growth of the Mn-Ni-Co precursor, forming a NP structure on the GO surface. The GO-MNCO precursor was effectively transformed into an rGO-MNCO hybrid nanostructure through calcination at 450°C . The enhanced SC performance of the rGO-MNCO electrode is attributed to the synergistic interaction between the rGO and multicomponent MNCO. In this hybrid nanostructure, rGO acts as a conductive substrate, characterized by a substantial surface area and exceptional flexibility. This configuration maximizes the SC performance of the multicomponent MNCO [53]. Rao et al. [44] described the synthesis of ternary iron-nickel-cobalt ZIF-67 composites (FeNiCo ZIF-67) through a co-precipitation method, exploring different molar concentrations of iron oxide, nickel oxide, and cobalt oxide to optimize the composite's properties (Figure 6B). Three distinct composites of FeNiCo ZIF-67 were synthesized with varying metal ratios of 1:1:1, 1:2:1, and 2:1:1. The FeNiCo ZIF-67 1:2:1 composite exhibited a substantial synergistic effect, resulting in enhanced

FIGURE 6: Schematic representation illustrating (A) the synthesis process for rGO-MNCO nanomaterial (Reproduced with permission from [53]. Copyright 2017, American Chemical Society); (B) the synthesis pathway for FeNiCo-derived ZIF-67 nanomaterials (Reproduced with permission from [44]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier); (C) the synthesis of $\text{NiCo}_{2-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_4$ NBs through a combination of chemical etching and cation exchange processes (Reproduced with permission from [194]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier); and (D) the synthesis process for the AC/NiCoSnO₄ nanocomposite (Reproduced with permission from [101]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier).

electrochemical performance. The enhancement in the electrochemically active surface area was ascribed to the material's porous polyhedral architecture. The FeNiCo ZIF-67 composites demonstrated an enhanced charge storage capacity, attributable to their superior electrical conductivity, increased electrochemically active surface area, and distinctive surface morphology [44]. Yang et al. [194] designed a suite of advanced techniques, including cation exchange and chemical etching, to synthesize trimetallic $\text{NiCo}_{2-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_4$ (NCFO) nanoboxes. Subsequently, a flexible electrode was fabricated by integrating NCFO with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) (Figure 6C). The ZIF-67 was utilized as a template to create TA (tannic acid)-Co complexes through a meticulous chemical etching process. This step was followed by the formation of TA-NiCoFe nanoballs (NBs) via cation exchange. Finally, the materials underwent annealing in air, resulting in the formation of a spinel

NCFO TTMO. Tannic acid serves as a powerful modifier due to its multiple phenolic hydroxyl groups, which grant it a strong ability to coordinate. These hydroxyl groups can effectively bond with the cobalt ions present in ZIF-67. Consequently, ZIF-67 can be transformed into a hollow structure through TA etching, resulting in the formation of TA-ZIF-67 nanobeads. Following the introduction of Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , TA-NiCoFe NBs were created via cation exchange, retaining the original cubic structure while featuring a hollow interior and a rough surface. The incorporation of rGO into NCFO enabled the formation of a flexible heterostructure, significantly enhancing electron transfer capabilities and offering an impressive specific capacitance [194]. Verma et al. [101] conducted a study on the synthesis of N-doped hierarchical porous activated carbon (AC) and NiCoSnO_4 (NCSO) (Figure 6D). These materials were produced using two techniques: pyrolysis for the

AC and a co-precipitation method for NiCoSnO₄. The approach utilized for synthesizing the AC/NCSO nanocomposite electrode from biowaste has proven to be an effective strategy for enhancing SC performance. The AC/NCSO nanocomposite demonstrated a uniform distribution of NCSO NPs on the porous AC matrix. These NCSO features were effectively integrated throughout the AC framework, highlighting the composite's structural integrity and potential for enhanced performance in SC applications. Consequently, the involvement of AC/NCSO nanocomposite in both EDLC and PC processes facilitates effective charge storage mechanisms [101]. Dolla et al. [43] synthesized ternary spinel Mn-substituted Mn_xZn_{1-x}Co₂O₄ (ZMCO) microspheres via an efficient coprecipitation method, subsequently subjected to calcination. The substitution of Mn results in a notable alteration in the dimensions of the ZMCO microspheres. The ZMC carbonate microspheres were synthesized using a straightforward coprecipitation technique that employed NH₄HCO₃ as the precipitating agent. Following the initial processing, the ZMC carbonate microspheres underwent calcination at 600°C. This treatment resulted in the successful formation of ZMCO microspheres. The calcination process played a key role in creating numerous pores by driving off gaseous H₂O and CO₂. This not only helped to eliminate these gases but also encouraged interactions among the individual NPs, ultimately leading to the formation of porous microspheres. The electrochemical performance of ZMCOs was evaluated for their application as electrode materials in SCs. The optimal performance was observed at a manganese concentration of $x = 0.7$, indicating that this specific compositional ratio facilitates enhanced electrochemical activity [43].

3.3. Electrodeposition. Electrodeposition is a highly effective synthetic method that enables the fabrication of nanostructures with exceptional uniformity and orientation. The nanostructures are securely anchored onto the metallic substrates, enabling the formation of stable films while effectively preventing the aggregation of structures caused by Ostwald ripening. The electrochemical bath is composed of the metal components intended for deposition. This method is notable for its simplicity, scalability, and affordability. The primary electrodeposition techniques employed in the fabrication of materials include potentiostatic, galvanostatic, and pulse plating methods. This technique represents a highly effective method for the binder-free, free-standing TMO nanostructures.

Singh et al. [102] utilized a simple technique to create self-standing vertically aligned arrays of highly porous 1D Co₃O₄-MnO₂-NiO composite nanotubes (NTs) on a conductive gold substrate. The process involved the template-based electrochemical deposition of Co-Mn-Ni alloy NTs, followed by a controlled oxidation step (Figure 7A). The electrodeposition process resulted in the uniform formation of high-density, well-aligned NT arrays. The average length and outer diameter of the NTs exhibit uniformity, ~12 and ~125 nm, respectively. Additionally, the wall thickness of the NTs ranges from ~10 to 15 nm. This hybrid NTs electrode features a unique design with a large accessible surface area and a minimal ion diffusion path. The combination of three redox-active materials on a

conductive metal substrate enhances charge transport, leading to improved electrochemical properties. This innovative NT array is ideal for SC applications due to its synergistic effects [102]. Seyed-Talebi et al. [103] prepared petal-like ternary nanosheets composed of Co_xNiV_yO_z, which were deposited on both bare and rGO-coated NF using a one-step electrodeposition method within a standard 3-electrode system (Figure 7B). Following this, the samples were calcined in a furnace at 300°C for 2 h. An aqueous solution containing cobalt sulfate heptahydrate, nickel sulfate hexahydrate, vanadium pentoxide, and sodium nitrate was prepared in a molar ratio of 1.5:1.5:2:3. This solution served as a precursor for the electrodeposition of petal-like Co_xNiV_yO_z nanosheets on the surface of an NF. The fabrication of 2D nanosheets from cobalt, nickel, and vanadium oxides significantly increased the number of electroactive sites, leading to a highly efficient SC. In a Co_xNiV_yO_z system, Co improves conductivity, while Ni increases capacity by enhancing active site density. Additionally, V offers excellent electrical conductivity and electrochemical performance, further boosting capacitive performance [103]. Hussain et al. [50] developed a binder-free 1D grass-like nanostructure on NF using an electrodeposition method followed by a post-calcination treatment (Figure 7C). Initially, metal ions were solubilized in a solution and subsequently deposited onto the NF via an electrodeposition technique. During mixing, potassium hydroxide dissociated into K⁺ and OH⁻ ions, while urea hydrolyzed to release OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻ ions in the aqueous media. The metal ions engaged with the anions to facilitate the vertical growth of trimetallic Mg-Ni-Co precursors on NF. The resulting Mg-Ni-Co precursors were subjected to thermal treatment to yield the trimetallic MNCO. The trimetallic MNCO nanostructures exhibit a grass-like morphology, characterized by lengths ranging from 700 to 900 nm and diameters of ~10–60 nm. Specifically, the tip diameters measure around 10 nm, while the root diameters reach about 60 nm. The MNCO trimetallic grass-like nanoneedles electrode demonstrated excellent SC performance [50].

Abebe and Ujihara [39] described binder-free electrodes composed of complex TMOs on NF. These electrodes were synthesized through a straightforward and cost-effective electrodeposition technique that utilized mixtures of nickel, cobalt, and manganese nitrates (Figure 7D). The materials deposited on the cathode and anode displayed distinct nanostructures: the cathode featured nanosheets, while the anode showcased block structures. The complex metal hydroxides were observed to precipitate as nanolayers on the NF cathode at a potential of -0.9 V. The metal ions were simultaneously oxidized and subsequently deposited in the form of blocks onto the NF anode. The quantities of Ni(NO₃)₂ and Mn(NO₃)₂ were maintained at 80 mM for Ni²⁺ and 40 mM for Mn²⁺, respectively, while the amount of Co(NO₃)₂ was varied, ranging from 20 to 120 mM. This variation had a notable impact on both the morphology and electrochemical properties of the resulting compounds. The electrochemical performance was influenced by variations in the molar ratio of Co:Ni:Mn, changing from 0.5:2:1 to 3:2:1. Furthermore, the ideal molar ratio of Ni:Mn:Co, along with the presence of three distinct cations in a single electrode, facilitated the movement of more electrons. This enhancement

FIGURE 7: Schematic representation outlining (A) the fabrication process for structured arrays of 1D hybrid NTs composed of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnO}_2\text{-NiO}$ (Reproduced with permission from [102]. Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society); (B) the trimetallic MNCO featuring a grass-like nanostructure (Reproduced with permission from [103]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier); (C) the electrochemical deposition of a ternary nanocomposite consisting of $\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{V}_z\text{O}_z$ onto a NF (Reproduced from [50]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier); and (D) the electrochemical deposition process for fabricating electrode material on NF (Reproduced from [39]).

significantly improved both electrical conductivity and electrochemical performance [39].

3.4. Microwave-Assisted Synthesis. The microwave-assisted heating approach is an efficient and practical technique for synthesizing nanomaterials. This method utilizes microwave radiation to rapidly heat the reaction mixture, allowing for precise control over temperature and reaction time. By enabling uniform heating, the process enhances the formation of NPs with desired properties and size distributions. Additionally, the use of microwaves often results in shorter synthesis times compared to conventional heating methods, leading to improved energy efficiency and reduced production costs. Overall, this approach provides a versatile and effective method for preparing a wide range of nanomaterials.

Lamiel et al. [104] developed hierarchical Ni-Co-Mn oxide nanoflakes synthesized directly on NF via an eco-friendly

microwave-assisted technique in an aqueous environment, followed by post-synthesis thermal treatment (Figure 8A). This method provides a simple and efficient approach to direct growth, eliminating the cumbersome slurry coating process. Key parameters were optimized by systematically varying the reaction time and concentration during the experiment. The Ni-Co-Mn-O was optimized under conditions of 10 mM concentration and 30 s, resulting in a hierarchical architecture that exhibited significant structural stability. This configuration comprises a conductive network of nanoflakes, which not only supports rapid ion transport but also maintains structural integrity during operation. The synergistic effects observed in the hierarchical Ni-Co-Mn-O nanoflakes led to exceptional electrochemical performance, highlighting their superior SC performance [104]. Sun et al. [195] developed tailored porous metal oxide nanowires using a microwave-assisted hydrothermal method

FIGURE 8: Schematic representation of (A) the synthesis of Ni-Co-Mn-O nanoflakes with varying morphologies as a function of precursor concentration (Reproduced with permission from [104]. Copyright 2017, Elsevier); (B) the synthesis methodology for fabricating metal oxide nanowires on an NF using an MHM (Reproduced with permission from [195]. Copyright 2021, Royal Society of Chemistry); and (C) the synthesis protocol for Mn-CCO porous nanowire arrays on NF (Reproduced with permission from [196]. Copyright 2022, Elsevier).

(MHM), which was subsequently subjected to an annealing process. The reaction was conducted in a microwave hydrothermal reactor at 140°C for 1 h, utilizing a power setting of 800 W and an annealing step in air at 400°C for 2 h (Figure 8B). The implementation of MHM improved the purity of the product compared to the traditional hydrothermal process (THP). The crystalline lattice of the precursor underwent expansion due to the effects of microwave treatment. In comparison to the THP variant, the MHM metal oxide demonstrated a distinct crystallographic structure and micromorphology. This difference played a key role in increasing both the withstand voltage range and the electronic conductivity of the electrode. The improvement in the electrochemical behavior of the MHM-assisted product was attributed to the expansion of its crystalline lattice and the optimized micromorphology resulting from the microwave treatment [195].

Sun et al. [196] conducted a microwave-assisted hydrothermal process, incorporating additional manganese sources to facilitate the doping of Mn into CoCo_2O_4 (Mn-CCO). The results demonstrated that manganese was successfully introduced via in situ isomorphic substitution within the porous CCO nanowires. In this procedure, the resultant solutions of

$\text{Mn}_x\text{CoCo}_2\text{O}_4$ were placed in a microwave autoclave and subjected to microwave heating at 140°C for 1 h at 800 W, followed by calcination at 400°C for 2 h under air (Figure 8C). The Mn-CCO material exhibited a network of densely packed porous nanowires that were uniformly distributed across the entire surface of the NF, resulting in well-defined nanowire arrays. The enlargement of the crystal parameters of CCO, facilitated by microwave assistance, has led to the in situ introduction of Mn as an isomorphic substitute within the CCO structure. The incorporation of Mn cations in the redox process significantly enhances the suppression of water splitting, effectively broadening the operational voltage range. The study found that the optimal amount of Mn-incorporated CCO nanowire array electrodes demonstrated outstanding SC performance [196].

3.5. Sol–Gel. The sol–gel process is an efficient technique that occurs at low temperatures, making it a cost-effective option for material synthesis. The sol–gel process is a chemical transformation that converts a liquid phase known as a “sol” into a solid network referred to as a “gel.” Following this transformation, a post-treatment phase occurs, resulting in the formation of solid metal oxides that contain ultrafine microcrystalline

particles. This method involves hydrolysis and condensation reactions. Several factors influence the condensation process, including the ratio of water to alkoxide, pH level, solvent choice, temperature, and the catalyst used. These parameters are crucial in determining the properties of the final material.

Dolla et al. [105] employed the sol-gel method to fabricate a carbon-coated ternary hybrid nanostructure consisting of Mn-Ni-Co-O NPs. The Mn-Ni-Co-O/C nanosheets were synthesized using Ni(Ac)₂, Co(Ac)₂, and Mn(Ac)₂ as metal precursors. In this process, NaCl served as a template, while citric acid acted as a complexing agent, and glucose was utilized as the carbon source. Notably, the ternary Mn-Ni-Co-O/C demonstrated enhanced electrochemical performance. Bhujun et al. [106] described an efficient sol-gel approach for synthesizing mixed TTM ferrites (MTTMF), specifically targeting nanocomposites of nickel-cobalt ferrite (NiCoF), copper-cobalt ferrite (CuCoF), and nickel-copper ferrite (NiCuF). The synthesis process leverages citric acid as a chelating agent, facilitating the formation of these MTTMF structures with desirable properties. During the synthesis process, the solution mixture was subjected to slow evaporation at 125°C, resulting in the formation of a viscous gel. Subsequently, the resulting thick slurry was heated to 600°C to yield the final product. The microstructural analysis of the MTTMF nanomaterials reveals that the interconnected clusters facilitate the formation of macropores. The study revealed the electrochemical performance of the various nanocomposites, indicating that the effectiveness was highest for CuCoF, followed by NiCoF, and then NiCuF [106]. Nabeel et al. [107] synthesized a composite material by integrating rGO with NiCoFe₂O₄ and the polypyrrole (PPy) via a sol-gel auto-combustion technique. In this study, citric acid was utilized as a fuel agent, while ammonia served as a pH stabilizer, with precise adjustments made to maintain the pH in the range of 7–8. The strategic integration of these materials leveraged their synergistic properties: rGO offered exceptional electrical conductivity and an expansive surface area, while NiCoFe₂O₄ contributed its PC performance. Additionally, PPy enhanced the composite with its conductivity and redox-active functionality. Besides, iron is known for its structural stability and affordability, while cobalt and nickel are recognized for their impressive redox activity. When combined, these elements harness their synergistic effects, significantly enhancing their energy storage capabilities [107].

3.6. CBD. The CBD method is an extensively employed technique for the efficient fabrication of various nanostructures. This approach facilitates the nucleation and growth of nanomaterials through controlled chemical reactions in solution, enabling the precise manipulation of their structural and compositional properties. This process involves immersing a substrate in a chemical solution containing metal ions and various reactants. This method facilitates the precise and controlled deposition of materials onto the substrate's surface. The parameters, including temperature, pH, and deposition duration, can be finely tuned to manipulate the morphology and characteristics of the resulting nanostructures. It is particularly advantageous due to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ability to

produce uniform coatings on various substrates, making it suitable for SC applications as an electrode.

For instance, Hussain et al. [108] developed a novel electrode material, known as Cu-Fe-Co ternary oxide (CFCO), in a unique nanoneedle structure (Figure 9A). This was achieved by incorporating co-cations (Cu-Fe) into the Co₃O₄ crystallites, utilizing a combination of CBD and hydrothermal techniques. Initially, cobalt cations, along with CO₃²⁻ and OH⁻ anions from urea in the solution, came together to form clusters of nanoneedles through a nucleation process. The process began with the treatment of the Co precursor/NF using a copper-containing solution, which resulted in the formation of the BTMO known as CCO. Following this, a separate solution containing both copper and iron was introduced to facilitate the creation of the TTMO, CFCO. This was achieved through a co-cation exchange reaction, which was subsequently followed by calcination. The subsequent incorporation of co-cations led to the development of a well-separated nanoneedle structure. The Cu-Fe-Co oxide nanoneedle structure demonstrated significantly better SC performance compared to the BTMO and STMO electrodes [108]. Zhu et al. [109] presented a simple approach for designing a ternary Al-Ni-Co oxide grown on NF. The AlNiCo-O material found on NF features ultrathin AlNiCo-O nanosheets that are intricately linked together, forming a 3D network that resembles a flower (Figure 9B). The combination of Ni, Co, and Al demonstrates significant synergistic electrochemical properties and offers additional multi-metal sites for redox activity. Consequently, the AlNiCo-O electrode demonstrates superior charge storage capabilities relative to the binary BTMO and STMO materials [109]. Chen et al. [110] investigated an easy and scalable CBD method, paired with calcination, to tailor 3D hierarchically porous ZnCO nanosheet arrays on NF (Figure 9C). In this CBD process, NF submerged a beaker filled with an aqueous solution of metal acetates and urea into an oven, maintaining the temperature at 90°C for 2 h. Ultimately, the fabricated metal precursor samples were subjected to annealing at 350°C for 2 h in argon to achieve hierarchically porous structures of ternary ZnCO nanosheets. The resulting ZnCo nanostructures are then assessed as a binder-free electrode for SC, demonstrating outstanding electrochemical performance [110]. Chen et al. [37] developed hierarchical Ni-Co-Mn-O nanosheets on NF utilizing a two-step synthesis approach that encompassed CBD followed by thermal annealing. In the CBD process, ammonium persulfate serves as an oxidizing agent that facilitates the entire reaction. At first, ternary metal-based hydroxide nanocrystals are produced in a supersaturated solution and then coated onto an NF. Subsequently, these NPs come together and self-organize into larger structures of nanosheets. Eventually, the precursor material, which is coated onto the NF, is heated in air at 350°C for 2 h, resulting in the formation of Ni-Co-Mn-O. The Ni-Co-Mn-O nanosheets serve as free-standing electrodes, demonstrating improved electrochemical performance owing to the synergistic effects of the Ni, Co, and Mn elements [37].

4. Advantages of TTMOs

Compared to STMOs and BTMOs, TTMOs provide several advantages that enhance their performance. One of the key

FIGURE 9: Schematic representation of (A) the synthesis pathway for CO, CCO, and CFCO nanomaterials (Reproduced with permission from [108]. Copyright 2020, Elsevier); (B) the process of forming ZNCO nanosheets on NF, accompanied by SEM images illustrating the ZNCO precursor nanosheets (Reproduced with permission from [110]. Copyright 2015, Royal Society of Chemistry); and (C) the procedure for synthesizing the Co₃O₄, NiCo₂O₄, and AlNiCo-O nanomaterials (Reproduced with permission from [109]. Copyright 2020, Elsevier).

benefits is the ability to engage in richer redox reactions, which contribute to more effective electrochemical processes. Additionally, TTMOs exhibit higher electrochemical activity, allowing for improved efficiency in SC applications. Their better conductivity is another significant advantage, arising from the synergistic effects that result from the coexistence of multiple metal species [54, 111]. Furthermore, the synergistic effects resulting from TTMOs, when combined with their distinct advantages, enhance the operational efficiency of SCs [46, 197]. These materials are favored for their scalable fabrication capabilities and exceptional adaptability in terms of morphology and structural configurations [31, 97]. Furthermore, TTMOs represent a promising strategy for enhancing electrochemical performance. The interaction among different

metallic elements plays a critical role in effectively modulating the 3D electronic structure. This capability enables the tuning of electronic properties, potentially leading to significant improvements in charge carrier dynamics and overall efficiency in electrochemical applications. The concurrent utilization of three distinct metal species plays a specific role for each element in the TTMO systems, enhancing the electrochemical performance [198, 199]. For instance, Maitra et al. [200] have reported Zn-Fe-Co oxide, where the enhancement in electronic conductivity and capacitance characteristics is attributed to the existence of Co and Fe ions. Meanwhile, the use of environmentally benign Zn contributes to improved electrical conductivity and structural integrity. Raghav et al. [201] investigated Mn-Co-Cu TTMO as the electrode material, revealing

TABLE 2: A comparative summary table illustrating the properties of TTMO, BTMO, and STMO.

Property	STMO	BTMO	TTMO
Composition	One metal combined with oxygen	Double metals combined with oxygen	Triple metals combined with oxygen
Cation diversity	Single cation	Two cations (form spinels, perovskites)	A minimum of three cations with adjustable stoichiometry
Structural complexity	Simple crystalline formations	Moderate complexity	High structural complexity; multiple cation sites
Oxygen vacancy formation	Relatively low	Moderate; depends on cation pairing	High tendency for oxygen vacancies → improved catalytic/electronic performance
Redox activity	Restricted to a single metal's redox pair	Multiple redox-active sites	Several synergistic redox pairs facilitate improved capacity
Electronic conductivity	Minimal to average	Enhanced through mixed valence configurations	Frequently elevated due to the combined effects of multiple metal interactions
Examples	NiO, CuO, TiO ₂ , etc.	NiMn ₂ O ₄ , NiCo ₂ O ₄ , CoMn ₂ O ₄ , etc.	MnNiCoO ₄ , Ru _x Ni _{1-x} Co ₂ O ₄ , Ni _(1-α) Co _(α) MoO ₄ , etc.

that the multiple oxidation states of Mn and Co provide a wide electrochemical potential window that enhances Faradaic charge transfer, while Cu boosts electrical conductivity. Sakkarapani and colleagues [32] studied Fe–Mn–Zn oxide, highlighting that Fe introduces defective sites that enhance intrinsic conductivity and electroactive ions, Mn offers multiple oxidation states for Faradaic reactions, and Zn contributes superior electrical conductivity and stability. In addition to their primary functions, the TTMO systems offer additional benefits that enhance their overall effectiveness and usability. Notably, Cu oxides have a broad potential window, but they become unstable during continuous electrochemical cycling. The presence of Ni and Mn can enhance the stability of the Cu within the TTMO due to strong interactions between these materials. Moreover, integrating Cu with other TM, particularly Ni and Zn, significantly improves its electrochemical stability within the TTMO system compared to systems based solely on Cu [198, 199]. Hence, TTMOs are becoming pivotal in advancing the technology of energy storage systems, enabling them to meet the growing requirements for both energy and power outputs in modern energy systems. A detailed comparative summary table, which outlines the key properties and characteristics of the three types of materials: TTMO, BTMO, and STMO. This information is consolidated in Table 2.

5. Design Strategies and Applications of TTMOs in SCs

5.1. TTMO Nanostructures. TTMOs are extensively investigated as electrode materials in SCs owing to their abundant availability and environmentally friendly characteristics. They possess several advantageous properties, including diverse structural motifs, chemical stability, high specific surface areas, and substantial theoretical specific capacitance values, making them compelling candidates for advanced energy storage applications [38, 45, 48]. In addition, the diminutive size and elevated concentration of cations in nanocrystalline structures enhance the kinetics of chemical reactions, leading to their increasing adoption as reactive nanocrystallites in contemporary applications [112, 202]. Due to their unique structure and

composition, SCs based on TTMOs frequently exhibit a broader operational voltage range. This characteristic not only enhances their versatility but also contributes to a significantly higher specific capacitance. Consequently, TTMOs enable an increased energy density, which is crucial for the development of high-performance SCs. We have compiled a comprehensive overview of the key findings from the literature in Table 1.

Wang et al. [203] have developed interactive polycrystalline TTMO nanoribbon electrodes (TTMORES) for constructing a solid-state supercapacitor (SSC), as illustrated in Figure 10A,B. The architecture consists of well-aligned vanadium oxide nanoribbon arrays (VORAs), synthesized from nickel oxide nanofibers and subsequently integrated with manganese oxide nanoparticles via a hydrothermal method that is both cost-effective and environmentally sustainable. These TTMOs maintain their crystallographic integrity during electrochemical cycling, exhibiting outstanding stability with 83.6% capacitance retention after 10,000 cycles. The electrodes demonstrate a specific capacitance of 788 F g⁻¹ at 5 mV s⁻¹. When assembled into SSC devices using triple-component electrodes, they achieve a notable energy density of 138 Wh kg⁻¹ at a power density of 450 W kg⁻¹. The nanografting technique facilitates the formation of reactive interfaces with interpenetrating channels, promoting efficient ion transport and enhancing electron conductivity throughout the electrodes [203]. Bahnasawya et al. [198] reported a cost-effective and facile methodology for synthesizing binder-free TTMO NPs utilizing earth-abundant elements, specifically copper, zinc, and nickel. This approach involves the preparation of a monolithic sub-100 nm mixed oxide by anodizing a German silver alloy (Cu–Zn–Ni) in an aqueous electrolyte for varying durations of 2, 5, and 8 min. The particle size and morphology were observed to be influenced by the duration of the anodization process. Upon evaluation of the electrochemical performance of these films as positive electrodes in a 1 M KOH solution, the film anodized for 5 min (designated as CZNO-5), with a composition of Cu₄Zn₂NiO_x@Cu–Zn–Ni, demonstrated exceptional areal and volumetric capacitances of ~27 mF cm⁻² and 3150 F cm⁻³, respectively, at a current density of 1 mA cm⁻². Furthermore,

FIGURE 10: The VORAs and TTMOREs serve as electrodes for SCs. (A) a simplified layout of the SSC indicates enhanced capacitance and energy density, (B) TTMOREs are chosen as promising energy storage systems because of their similar or superior potential window and strong crystallographic structure (Reproduced with permission from [203]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier); (C) CV curves of the negatode (B-AC) and positode (CZNO-5) at 50 mV s^{-1} in a 3-electrode system, (D) evaluation of the long term cycling performance of the CZNO-5//B-AC device at 10 mA cm^{-2} , and (E) comparison of Ragone plots across different current densities alongside a range of devices reported in the literature (Reproduced with permission from [198]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier).

when assembled into a solid-state SC device in conjunction with bioderived AC (B-AC), the CZNO-5 exhibited a capacitance of 3.8 mF cm^{-2} at the same current density, along with a notable rate capability of $\sim 35\%$ at 5 mA cm^{-2} . The specific energy and specific power of the CZNO-5//B-AC device were measured to be $0.97 \text{ } \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ and 0.91 mW cm^{-2} , respectively. Importantly, unlike many copper-based devices, the CZNO-5//B-AC configuration demonstrated exceptional durability, retaining 100% and 89.6% of its initial capacitance after 3800 and 5000 consecutive charge/discharge cycles, respectively (Figure 10C–E) [198].

Yaseen et al. [204] synthesized a TTMO material designated as Zn–Cu–Mn–O utilizing a simple composite hydroxide-mediated (CHM) approach, which integrates zinc, copper, and manganese to facilitate a variety of Faradaic reactions through multiple oxidation states. This innovation enhances both the energy density and electrical conductivity of SCs. A key aspect of this material is the ability of manganese

species to cycle through multiple oxidation states ($\text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$), which significantly contributes to its energy storage capabilities. During the oxidation process, metal ions such as Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} are mobilized from the electrode material into the electrolyte. The nanosheet-like structure of the composite offers a large specific surface area, accompanied by numerous channels that facilitate rapid ion transfer and electron migration between the electrolyte and the electrode. The synthesized ZnCuMn–O nanosheet architecture was employed as an electrode for SCs, demonstrating a distinguished capacity of $326.25 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ at a specific current density of 1.5 A g^{-1} . This exceptional capacitance is complemented by impressive rate capability and outstanding cycle stability, retaining 86.4% of its initial capacity after 7000 cycles. Additionally, the ZnCuMn–O//AC HSC device achieved a satisfactory energy density of 44.34 Wh kg^{-1} at a power density of 995.67 W kg^{-1} , along with excellent capacitance retention of 89.6% and a coulombic efficiency of 97.2% after 5000 GCD

FIGURE 11: Continued.

FIGURE 11: Schematic representation of (A) ZnCuMn-O//AC HSC cell, (B, C) energy storage process of the ZnCuMn-O//AC during charging/discharging, (D) CV profiles of ZnCuMn-O and AC, (E) comparison of the Ragone plot of ZnCuMn-O//AC HSC with previously reported data, (F) the cycling stability of ZnCuMn-O//AC HSC (the GCD curves shown in the inset image of the last fifteen cycles), (G) Nyquist plots before and after cycling performance of ZnCuMn-O//AC HSC device (Reproduced with permission from [204]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier); (H) CV profiles of the NCMO@NiCo-MOF//AC ASC at 5 mV s⁻¹, (I) the capacitive and ion-diffusion contribution graphs of NCMO@NiCo-MOF//AC ASC, (J) the correlation between energy and power densities of NCMO@NiCo-MOF//AC systems, (K) long-term cycling stability of ASC at 5 A g⁻¹ (Reproduced with permission from [113]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier); (L) CV curves of Ni-Co-Mn-O SSC, (M, N) GCD and cycling test (inset: the LED lighted during the discharge), and (O) Ragone plots presented in both the existing literature and the current work (Reproduced with permission from [104]. Copyright 2017, Elsevier).

cycles. Additionally, the slight variations observed in the resistance characteristics before and after cycling suggest that the HSC device continues to exhibit robust conductivity. Comprehensive electronic property investigations conducted through density functional theory (DFT) calculations further substantiate the exceptional potential of the ZnCuMn-O electrode material. The insights derived from these DFT predictions indicate that the ZnCuMn-O interface electrode exhibits superior conductivity, which is advantageous for both cyclability and rate efficiency (Figure 11A–G) [204]. Qing et al. [113] fabricated NCMO TTMO nanoflowers, which served as a substrate for the subsequent directional growth of NiCo-MOF nanosheets on their surface. This oriented growth effectively mitigated agglomeration, resulting in the formation of NCMO@NiCo-MOF, which boasts enhanced electrochemical

sensitivity and a significant increase in active sites. When employed as an electrode, the NCMO@NiCo-MOF achieves a substantial contact area with the electrolyte, resulting in a higher specific capacitance of 1724 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹. The material exhibits a PC contribution (ion diffusion) to the ASC at 100 mV s⁻¹, accounting for 78% of the overall capacity. Additionally, an ASC constructed from NCMO@NiCo-MOF and AC achieves a power density of 824.8 W kg⁻¹, delivering a high energy density of 44.5 Wh kg⁻¹ (Figure 11H–K). The unique 3D architecture of the composite includes numerous reactive sites, which facilitate electron transfer processes and enhance the electrochemical performance of the NCMO material [113]. Lamiel et al. [104] demonstrated an efficient method for synthesizing NCMO on NF through low-power microwave irradiation. By fine-tuning the precursor concentration and

irradiation time, NCMO oxide nanoflakes were successfully formed. Optimal conditions, specifically, 10 mM concentration for 30 s, yielded a hierarchical structure that provided a stable framework and a conductive network of nanoflakes, enabling rapid ion transport without structural degradation. The synergistic interactions among the NCMO contributed to a remarkable specific capacitance of 2536 F g^{-1} at a current density of 5 mA cm^{-2} (6.49 A g^{-1}) when tested in a mixed KOH/ $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ electrolyte. In cyclic performance assessments, the SSC device demonstrated 73.5% capacitance retention after 5000 cycles at 2.0 mA cm^{-2} . Moreover, three SSC devices were configured in series and charged for just 1 min using a 9 V power source, revealing the LED's brightness during discharge initiation and after 30 s. The SSC devices also exhibited impressive metrics, including a capacitance of 298 F g^{-1} , an energy density of 41.4 Wh kg^{-1} , and a power density of 5.4 kW kg^{-1} , as displayed in Figure 11L–O [104].

5.2. Doped TTMO Nanostructures. In the realm of structural optimization strategies aimed at enhancing the electrochemical performance of TMOs, one effective approach is heteroatom doping. This method complements other strategies, such as microstructural adjustments and the formation of hybrid architectures, to further enhance the performance metrics of these materials [114, 205]. Doping serves as an effective strategy to enhance the electrical conductivity, chemical characteristics, and reactivity of electrode materials. This process involves altering the charge states and band gaps of the compounds, which in turn optimizes their performance in SC applications [95, 115]. Usually, doping can be categorized into two key mechanisms: (1) adsorption, which involves the attachment of metal or organic species onto the surface of materials, and (2) substitutional doping, where heteroatoms or heteroions, comprising nonmetal atoms or metal ions, are incorporated into the host lattice of the electroactive material. This process significantly alters the electronic properties and enhances the functionality of the host system [116]. Besides, precisely doping a specific content of heteroatoms or functional groups into the material can significantly enhance its structural characteristics. This integration can lead to the establishment of vacancies, fill existing voids, or allow for fine-tuning of the lattice configuration, thereby optimizing the material's properties [197]. Thus, it can significantly enhance the material's efficiency in energy storage and its kinetics in reaction processes [117].

Hussain et al. [118] prepared Cu–Ni–Co oxide (CNCO) featuring agglomerated nanoneedle-like morphologies in the initial phase. Subsequently, they incorporated boron doping to achieve a structurally modified variant, referred to as CNCO-D-SD. The boron-doped agglomerated nanoneedle-like structures retained their merged tip morphology; however, a corresponding decrease in stability was observed. The incorporation of boron was assessed in a single step, which intriguingly led to the formation of self-organized, boron-doped CNCO (CNCO-D-SO) structures exhibiting 1D vertically aligned nanoneedle morphology. Boric acid served both as a dopant and a structural-directing agent. The CNCO-D-SO demonstrated enhanced electrochemical performance compared to the CNCO and CNCO-D-SD variants. The capacity

contribution of CNCO-D-SO is predominantly influenced by diffusion-controlled redox reactions, accounting for 71% of the total, while capacitive currents contribute the remaining 29%. This distribution highlights its characteristics as a BT energy storage mechanism. Interestingly, the HSC constructed using CNCO-D-SO//rGO demonstrated outstanding cyclic stability, retaining 87% capacity after 8000 cycles. In comparison, the CNCO-D-SD//rGO configuration exhibited a lower retention of 46% after 5000 cycles, while the bare CNCO//rGO system showed only 53% retention after the same number of cycles (Figure 12A–D). Thus, this work exhibited that doping enhances both the stability and capacity of CNCO. However, the intrinsic properties of the active materials play a crucial role in achieving optimal performance outcomes [118]. Chakraborty et al. [119] presented an efficient hydrothermal approach for the in situ synthesis of Mn-doped NiCoFeO_4 hierarchical nanostructures resembling flowers, directly onto NF. Mn was selected as a dopant due to its oxides exhibiting exceptional PC behavior, making it one of the most extensively researched oxides as a SC electrode material. The Mn-doped NiCoFeO_4 , mounted on NF, demonstrated superior performance as an electrode material compared to its undoped counterpart during three-terminal electrochemical assessments. It achieved a specific capacitance of 500 mF cm^{-2} at a current density of 5 mA cm^{-2} , marking a fivefold increase over the undoped NiCoFeO_4 , which exhibited a specific capacitance of only 99 mF cm^{-2} . Additionally, the Mn-doped variant maintained an impressive capacity retention of 83% after 7500 cycles at a higher current density of 25 mA cm^{-2} , underscoring the significant impact of Mn doping on its electrochemical stability and performance. Furthermore, an all-solid-state ASC was developed using a hierarchical Mn-doped NiCoFeO_4 as the positive electrode, paired with a commercial AC as the negative electrode. This configuration achieved a power density of 2 mW cm^{-2} at an energy density of $60 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$, successfully powering an LED for a duration of 3 min (Figure 12E,F) [119].

Hussain et al. [108] demonstrated the successful incorporation of cations (Cu) and co-cations (Cu–Fe) into cobalt oxide crystallites through a CBD technique, followed by high-temperature calcination to achieve the desired structural characteristics. Notably, the nanoneedle architecture of the synthesized Cu–Fe–Co TTMO exhibited exceptional structural stability post-calcination, maintaining its crystal phase throughout the cation exchange process. The specific capacity of the Cu–Fe–Co TTMO nanoneedle configuration was measured at 737.2 C g^{-1} under a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , significantly surpassing the capacities of pristine CO (504 C g^{-1}) and CCO (632 C g^{-1}). The findings demonstrate the enhanced performance of the Cu–Fe–Co TTMO electrode. The substantial capacity of the Cu–Fe–Co TTMO electrode highlights that the synergistic interactions among cobalt, iron, and copper significantly enhance its performance compared to both its STMO and BTMO counterparts. The Cu–Fe–Co TTMO electrode exhibited a minimal degradation rate of 0.000238% per cycle over 4200 charge–discharge cycles. A constructed HSC achieved an impressive energy density of 48 Wh kg^{-1} along with a power density of 4800 W kg^{-1} . The integration of the HSC device with solar cells successfully illuminated 52 red

FIGURE 12: (A) Evaluation of CV profiles of various electrode at 10 mV s^{-1} , (B) comparison of GCD profiles of diverse electrode at 4 A g^{-1} , (C) capacity contribution of CNCO-D-SO, (D) schematic diagram illustrating the transport of electrons and ions, as well as the adhesion mechanisms occurring between the substrate and the active materials (Reproduced with permission from [118]. Copyright 2021, American Chemical Society); (E) schematic pictogram of the M-NCFO//AC ASC device, and (F) digital image of the M-NCFO//AC ASC system lighting up a red LED (Reproduced with permission from [119]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier); (G) schematic representation of Cu-Fe-Co TTMO//AC HSC device, and (H) schematic depiction of the energy transfer process for charging the energy storage device utilizing photovoltaic panels, followed by its discharge to illuminate a light bulb (Reproduced with permission from [108]. Copyright 2020, Elsevier).

LEDs (Figure 12G,H), thereby demonstrating the feasibility of the prepared electrodes for both practical applications and commercial deployment [108].

Merum et al. [92] synthesized porous 3D oval cobalt-doped nickel vanadate (NCVO) electrode materials via a streamlined one-step hydrothermal process. Cobalt doping combined with the formation of porous 3D oval architectures significantly enhances the electrical conductivity of the electrode material. The porous morphology not only facilitates the infiltration of electrolyte within the 3D structures but also minimizes the ionic transport pathway, thereby optimizing the electrochemical performance for charge storage, encompassing both Faradaic and capacitive mechanisms. The interconnectivity of the particles, combined with the porous structure of each oval-shaped particle, enhances the accessibility of active species and facilitates improved charge transfer kinetics. The incorporation of cobalt dopants enhances electronic conductivity and significantly augments redox chemistry interactions. Consequently, NCVO exhibited a specific capacitance of 391 F g^{-1} at 0.5 A g^{-1} and 376 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} , coupled with an impressive capacitance retention of 98.6% following 8000 charge–discharge cycles. This performance underscores its exceptional cycling stability. Besides, the micro-spherical layered-structured BiOBr electrode was selected as the negative electrode and exhibited a distinctive specific capacitance of 132 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} within the potential range of -1 to $+0 \text{ V}$. Furthermore, the solid-state HSC device composed of NCVO//BiOBr exhibited a specific capacitance of 118 F g^{-1} , an energy density of 25.5 Wh kg^{-1} , and impressive cycle stability, maintaining 85.9% of its original capacitance after 10,000 charge–discharge cycles (Figure 13A–D) [92]. Zheng et al. [197] reported the synthesis of 1D cobalt-based metal-organic framework (Co-MOF) nanorods, which were grown on a CC utilizing the solution immersion technique. These nanorods served as precursors for further processing. Subsequently, $\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4@\text{CC}$ (NCCO@CC) was synthesized through a combination of methodologies, including a hydrothermal synthesis approach, followed by high-temperature annealing, and culminating in a one-step phosphorization technique. The hierarchical 1D/2D P-doped NCCO@CC architecture enhances the availability of active sites and promotes effective electrolyte ion diffusion. By harnessing the extensive specific surface area of Co-MOF, along with the synergistic interactions from the incorporation of Ni, Co, and Cu, and the enhanced active sites due to P-doping, the resulting electrode material demonstrates outstanding electrochemical performance. Theoretical models suggest that P-doping plays a crucial role in optimizing the electronic structure, enhancing conductivity, and increasing the adsorption energy of OH^- ions. The theoretical findings were validated through electrochemical testing. Notably, the optimized P- $\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4$ demonstrated an exceptional capacitance of 2872.1 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} , representing a significant enhancement of 1.58 times compared to the pre-phosphating value of 1810.6 F g^{-1} . Moreover, an HSC device utilizing 9-P-NCCO@CC was tailored, achieving a notable energy density of 71.6 Wh kg^{-1} coupled with a power density of 800 W kg^{-1} . The device exhibited striking cyclic stability, retaining 87.73% of its initial capacitance after 10,000

charge–discharge cycles (Figure 13E–H) [197]. Zhang et al. [115] reported the synthesis of Cu-doped Ni–Co-based electrode materials utilizing a hydrothermal method followed by an annealing step. The distinct nanocone morphology stands in stark contrast to the nanorod formation observed in the Ni–Co precursor electrode, suggesting that the incorporation of Cu dopants significantly influences the structural characteristics of the resulting compound electrode. The experimental findings indicate that the nanocone-like Cu-doped Ni–Co oxide (Ni–Co–Cu oxide) electrodes exhibit superior area-specific capacities of 6.54 F cm^{-2} at 3 A g^{-1} . These values represent ~ 2.5 times the area-specific capacity of the undoped nanorod-like Ni–Co precursor electrode, which has a capacity of 2.51 F cm^{-2} under the same conditions. The enhancements in performance can be attributed to the presence of abundant oxygen defects in the Cu-doped oxide structure. Furthermore, the quasi-solid-state ASCs utilizing Ni–Co–Cu–O//AC configurations demonstrated impressive energy densities of 42.1 Wh kg^{-1} , while operating at power densities of 374.9 W kg^{-1} . These performance metrics enable the devices to power a red LED for ~ 8 and 11 min, respectively (Figure 13I–L). Thus, Cu-doping significantly alters the morphology and defect profile of a Ni–Co bimetallic compound electrode, while concurrently enhancing its electrical conductivity and overall electrochemical performance [115].

Li et al. [120] introduced an innovative approach for designing high-performance HSCs by synergistically optimizing vanadium-doped self-supported 3D flower-like $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ structures via a microwave-assisted hydrothermal approach. This approach exhibits enhanced electrochemical performance due to several factors, including vanadium doping, which introduces oxygen vacancies, lattice distortion effects, and the inherent self-supporting characteristics of its 3D floral architecture. Vanadium doping resulted in a noticeable enhancement in both the peak current and peak area in the CV curves of the flower-like $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ structure. This suggests that the incorporation of vanadium improves the redox activity and facilitates charge transfer kinetics within the material. The GCD profiles indicate that the vanadium-doped flower-like $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ exhibits the most prolonged charging and discharging durations, underscoring its superior electrochemical performance. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) results demonstrate that vanadium doping significantly enhances the electrical conductivity of the material, refines ion diffusion pathways, and improves overall electrochemical characteristics. Consequently, the synergistic interplay between vanadium doping and the self-supported flower-like morphology substantially boosts the electrochemical performance of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ electrodes. The vanadium-doped flower-like $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ material exhibits an incredible specific capacitance of 2157 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} . Notably, even after 10,000 cycles at a current density of 15 A g^{-1} , the capacitance retention remains an impressive 98.2%. Moreover, the V- $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ // SnO_2 /CNT HSC exhibits an impressive energy density of 151 Wh kg^{-1} at 3 A g^{-1} , representing a 30%–60% improvement over traditional molybdate capacitors. Additionally, it exhibits considerable capacitance retention, maintaining 96.2% stability after 10,000 charge–discharge cycles (Figure 13M–P) [120].

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

(E)

(F)

(G)

(H)

FIGURE 13: Continued.

FIGURE 13: Continued.

FIGURE 13: (A) GCD profiles of NCVO//BiOBr HSC device at diverse current densities, (B) cycling performance graph at 6 A g^{-1} (inset: GCD of the first and last five cycles), (C, D) emission of light from a green and red LEDs (Reproduced with permission from [92]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier); (E) the schematic representation of 9-P-NCCO@CC//AC HSC fabrication, (F) GCD profiles of HSC device, (G) snapshots of 10 white LED power-driven by three HSC systems, (H) cycling performance and Coulombic efficiency of the HSC device (Reproduced with permission from [197]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier); (I) comparison of CV of the AC and Ni–Co–Cu electrodes at 10 mV s^{-1} , (J) CV graph of Ni–Co–Cu–O//AC ASC under diverse sweep rates, (K) GCD profiles of Ni–Co–Cu–O//AC ASC under dissimilar current densities, (L) cyclic retention of ASCs (inset: illuminating a LED) (Reproduced with permission from [115]. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society); (M, N) CVs and GCD profiles of diverse electrodes, (O) comparison of specific capacitance across various electrode materials, (P) Nyquist plots of diverse electrodes (Reproduced with permission from [120]. Copyright 2025, Wiley-VCH).

5.3. Composite/Hybrid TTMO Nanostructures. The effective design of SCs relies on understanding the structural and compositional properties of electrode materials. By analyzing and tailoring these properties, one can enhance the electrochemical performance of SCs. This involves selecting suitable materials and engineering their architecture at molecular and macro levels to achieve high energy and power densities, as well as improved charge–discharge cycles for advanced applications [121, 122]. Thus, the integration of TTMOs using an organic/inorganic hybridization approach with carbon-based materials and conducting polymers effectively addresses the limitations of each component. This method enhances synergistic interactions between the two, leveraging their complementary properties for better performance [47, 100, 107, 123, 124]. Carbon materials serve as a substrate for transitioning TTMO nanostructures, providing essential structural support to maintain the integrity of the hybrid composites [53, 105]. Additionally, the integration of carbon with TTMOs may establish a conductive pathway, significantly mitigating the impacts of volume expansion during cycling [125]. Conducting polymers are favored due to their cost-effectiveness, excellent electrical conductivity, significant redox activity, and decreased diffusion distance for electrolytes [126]. Composite or hybrid nanostructures are engineered to minimize metal ion leaching from TTMOs during redox reactions, thereby reducing the risk of electrode failure due to metal dissolution or surface damage. By preserving the structural integrity and performance of electrodes, these nanostructures enhance the longevity and reliability of electrochemical devices [101].

For example, Raghav et al. [201] investigated the electrochemical characteristics of hybrid nanostructures designed for high-performance SCs. They synthesized flower-like nanostructures composed of TTMOs, specifically manganese,

copper, and cobalt, utilizing a hydrothermal synthesis approach. The MCC nanostructures were modified with other TMO NPs using direct current magnetron sputtering techniques for the SC electrode. The presence of various multivalent metal ions enhances the density of redox-active sites, while the hybrid characteristics of the nanostructures contribute to an increased electrochemically active surface area. These synergistic interactions lead to a significant improvement in electrode performance. Additionally, the direct fabrication of flower-like hybrid nanostructures on NF enhances mechanical adhesion, thereby increasing the stability of the electrodes during electrochemical cycling. The optimized electrode achieves a specific capacitance of 2261 F g^{-1} at 1 mV s^{-1} . Moreover, the fabricated solid-state SSC device exhibits excellent cycling stability, with a capacitance retention of 97% after 2000 charge–discharge cycles, alongside an energy density of 106 Wh kg^{-1} at a power density of 3236.3 W kg^{-1} (Figure 14A–D) [201]. Singh et al. [102] employed a facile technique to grow free-standing vertically aligned arrays of highly porous 1D $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{–MnO}_2\text{–NiO}$ hybrid NTs (HNTs) on a conducting gold substrate for the fabrication of SC electrodes. These HNTs are fabricated by combining a simple AAO template-based electrochemical deposition of Co–Mn–Ni alloy NTs followed by controlled oxidation. Notably, the SC electrode featuring highly ordered, vertically aligned, porous 1D arrays of ternary HNTs exhibits exceptional electrochemical performance, achieving a specific capacitance of $\sim 2525 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ within a 0.8 V potential window. This performance is attributed to the innovative electrode architecture and the synergistic interplay of the three TMOs integrated within a hybrid framework (Figure 14E–H). Furthermore, the electrode exhibits excellent long-term cycling stability, along with high energy and power density characteristics [102]. Sahoo et al. [127] reported the synthesis of a 3D

FIGURE 14: Continued.

FIGURE 14: Continued.

FIGURE 14: Electrochemical performance of solid-state SSC configured exploiting MCC_Cr_65W electrodes and PVA/KOH electrolyte: (A) Schematic depiction of the SSC system, (B) GCD profiles at diverse current densities, (C) a disparity of ED combined with PD (inset: LED energized by the device), (D) cyclic stability assessment conducted over 2000 charge/discharge cycles (Reproduced with permission from [38]. Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society); (E) GCD profiles for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-MnO}_2\text{-NiO}$ HNTs electrodes, (F) Analysis of the variation in areal and specific capacitance as a function of current density, (G) the Nyquist plot for 1D HNTs electrode with the Bode plot included as an inset, (H) cycling performance and Coulombic efficiency throughout 5700 charge/discharge cycles with an inset showing the final five charge-discharge cycles (Reproduced with permission from [102]. Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society); (I) schematic illustration of Fe-Ni-Co-O//rGO HSC, (J) CV curves of rGO and Fe-Ni-Co-O at 20 mV s^{-1} , (K) comparison of the Ragone plot for the Fe-Ni-Co-O//rGO HSC against established data in the literature (the inset displays the “YU” logo illuminated by 19 individual LEDs), (L) cycling stability over 5000 cycles (Reproduced with permission from [127]. Copyright 2018, Elsevier); and (M) GCD profiles of ZCN-2//AC ASC, and (N) energizing a green LED (Reproduced with permission from [128]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier).

binder-free ternary Fe-Ni-Co oxide (FNCO) hybrid nanoflake array directly on NF through a facile two-step process. This method leverages the unique properties of the metal oxide constituents to enhance structural integrity and electrochemical performance. The FNCO nanoflakes demonstrated enhanced electrochemical performance due to the synergistic interactions among the various transition metals present in the hybrid nanoarchitecture. The synthesized SC electrode exhibited impressive electrochemical characteristics, achieving a high specific capacitance of 867 F g^{-1} . Additionally, it demonstrated exceptional cycling stability, with a capacitance retention of 92.3% after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles. The developed HSC device demonstrated an impressive energy density of 40 Wh kg^{-1} while maintaining capacitance retention of 87.4% of its initial performance after 5000 charge-discharge cycles. The HSC device exemplifies its practical applications as two fully charged HSC devices were connected in series to power 19 LEDs (Figure 14I-L) [127]. Zhu et al. [128] utilized a seed-mediated approach to synthesize a double-template ZIF-8@ZIF-67 featuring a core-shell architecture. This layered structure serves as a sacrificial template for subsequent processing steps. Following the solvent thermal loading procedure and subsequent calcination, ZIF-8@ZIF-67 underwent etching and was successfully transformed into a TTMO composite comprising ZnO, Co_3O_4 , and NiO. The optimized ZnO/ $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{/NiO-2}$ (ZCN-2) exhibits superior morphological characteristics and electrochemical performance, which can be attributed to the precise incorporation of inorganic salts. This precise adjustment not only enhances its structural integrity but also significantly improves its electrochemical efficiency. The ZCN-2 exhibits an impressive specific capacitance of 1119.11 C g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} . Furthermore, even at a heightened current density of 10 A g^{-1} , the material retains 93.75% of its capacitance after undergoing 5000 cycles of charge-discharge, demonstrating excellent cycling stability and retention of electrochemical performance. The assembled ZCN-2//AC ASC

achieves a notable maximum energy density of 95.82 Wh kg^{-1} , highlighting its significant performance. After undergoing 10,000 charge and discharge cycles at 10 A g^{-1} , the ASC retains 94.53% of its original performance. Additionally, when charged, a setup with two ASCs can successfully power an LED for up to 30 min (Figure 14M,N) [128].

Rose et al. [206] developed a novel method for repurposing the noxious weed *Parthenium hysterophorus* (PH) into ultra-high surface area carbon for use in capacitive electrodes. This approach enables the fabrication of high-performance ASCs that utilize binder-free PC electrodes composed of TTMOs, such as Ni-Co-Mn-O (TTMO-1) and Ni-Co-Zn-O (TTMO-2), thereby significantly enhancing their electrochemical performance and efficiency (Figure 15A-D). The TTMOs (TMO-1 and TMO-2) were synthesized via a one-pot hydrothermal method and annealing. In a three-electrode setup, TTMO-1 and TTMO-2 exhibited excellent capacitances, with stored charges of 557.23 and 628.22 C g^{-1} at 0.5 A g^{-1} , respectively. Furthermore, the ASC cell configuration utilizing PH-900-K as the anode and TTMO-1 or TTMO-2 as the cathode achieved a peak energy density of 49.29 Wh kg^{-1} for the TTMO-1//PH-900-K setup. In contrast, the TTMO-2//PH-900-K configuration reached a higher maximum energy density of 70.86 Wh kg^{-1} [206]. Yang et al. [129] described the synthesis of Zn-Cu-Co-O (ZCCO) spinel structures, achieving tunable morphologies through a straightforward hydrothermal method and subsequent post-calcination. The ultra-thin 2D nanosheets provide substantial surface area advantages, facilitating rapid mass transport and efficient ion transfer. This results in an improved electrode material utilization ratio during electrochemical processes, enhancing overall performance. Therefore, the 2D ZCCO nanosheets exhibit promising characteristics for use as electrodes in SC applications. Interestingly, the 2D ZCCO quasi-nanosheets exhibit a specific capacitance of 669 C g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} and retain 339 C g^{-1} at 30 A g^{-1} , showcasing excellent rate capability. They also maintain 96% of their

FIGURE 15: Continued.

FIGURE 15: Continued.

FIGURE 15: (A) Ragone plots of the constructed ASCs, (B) ASC tailored utilizing synthesized two TTMOs and AC from biomass, (C, D) cycle stability of TMO-1//PH-900-K and TMO-2//PH-900-K (inset: the graph depicting the first 100 cycles) (Reproduced with permission from [206]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier); (E) schematic illustration of the ZCCO//AC ASC system, (F) CV profiles of ZCCO and AC at 50 mV s^{-1} , (G) cyclic stability assessment over a duration of 10,000 cycles, (H) Nyquist plot (pre- and post-cyclic) (Reproduced with permission from [129]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier); (I) CV curves of ZCMG and AC electrodes at 20 mV s^{-1} , (J, K) CV and GCD profiles of ZCMG//AC ASC, (L) cycling stability test of ASC (inset: image depicting the operation of a driving LED) (Reproduced from [130]); (M) CV curves of rGO and rGO-MNCO electrodes at 2 mV s^{-1} , (N, O) CV profiles of the rGO-MNCO//rGO ASC device under diverse potential range and scan rates, and (P) GCD curves of the rGO-MNCO//rGO device at varied current densities (Reproduced with permission from [53]. Copyright 2017, American Chemical Society).

initial capacitance after 5000 cycles at 30 A g^{-1} , highlighting their impressive cycling stability. Additionally, the ZCCO//AC ASC achieves an energy density of 55.1 Wh kg^{-1} at 1280 W kg^{-1} while retaining 94.9% of its capacity after 10000 cycles at 30 A g^{-1} . The modest rise in total resistance observed following cyclic stability testing indicates that the electrode material exhibits a stable performance characteristic (Figure 15E–H) [129]. Liu et al. [130] reported the electrode materials for SCs utilizing Zn–Co–Mo–rGO (ZCMG) and Zn–Co–Mo (ZCM) synthesized on the NF via a one-step hydrothermal method. The incorporation of rGO effectively modified the nanosheet morphology, enhancing the specific surface area and augmenting conductivity, both of which are advantageous for facilitating the redox reactions within the SC. Consequently, the ZCMG electrode material exhibited a specific capacity of 1189 F g^{-1} (713 C g^{-1}), outperforming ZCM's 492 F g^{-1} (295 C g^{-1}) at 1 A g^{-1} . ZCMG also showed a rate performance of 80.2%, compared to ZCM's 69.1%. The selected operating voltage range of 0–1.5 V is determined from the CVs of the ZCMG//AC ASCs evaluated at various voltage levels. In a ZCMG//AC ASC, it reached a maximum specific capacity of 68 C g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} and maintained an impressive capacity retention rate of 95% after 1000 cycles, highlighting its excellent cycling stability. The ZCMG//AC device demonstrated an energy density of 14 Wh kg^{-1} at a power density of 750 W kg^{-1} , sustaining an energy density of 5.23 Wh kg^{-1} even at a high-power density of 7.5 kW kg^{-1} . Additionally, two ASCs were connected in series. After charging, the device powered the red LED for at least 120 s, showcasing potential applications of ASC devices (Figure 15I–L) [130].

Wu et al. [53] synthesized hybrid nanostructured rGO nanosheet-supported Mn–Ni–Co TTMO (MNCO) electrodes through a simple co-precipitation method, followed by a calcination step. In this hybrid nanoarchitecture, rGO nanosheets

serve as a 2D conductive substrate for MNCOs, significantly enhancing surface area and accelerating ion diffusion due to lower energy barriers. This synergy maximizes the SC performance of the MNCOs. Impressively, electrochemical evaluations show that rGO significantly enhances the SC performance of the MNCO electrode compared to its pure counterpart (Figure 15M–P). The rGO-MNCO composite exhibits a specific capacitance of 646.1 C g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} , with $\sim 89.6\%$ retention at 30 A g^{-1} , demonstrating its excellent rate capability. When configured as an ASC device, the rGO-MNCO//rGO system demonstrates a peak energy density of 35.6 Wh kg^{-1} and an impressive power density of 5548.9 W kg^{-1} , while achieving a Coulombic efficiency of 100% and maintaining a capacitance retention of 77.2% over 10,000 cycles [53].

6. Structural and Mechanical Degradation of TTMO

The in-depth examination of the structural and mechanical degradation after rigorous cycle performance of the TTMO is another critical concern when evaluating the feasibility of the modern industrial sector. For example, Yaseen et al. [204] tested the ZnCuMn-O electrode using ex situ characterizations after long-term cycling to examine the charge storage evolution process. The GCD profiles remained stable after 7000 cycles, although there were minor potential drops due to active material loss resulting from breakdown, redox dissolution, and electrolyte corrosion. Mechanical stress also caused material detachment, which reduced the electrode's surface area and increased resistance. The Nyquist plot for the ZnCuMn-O electrode demonstrates minimal variations in both the series resistance (R_s) and the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) before and after the stability test, suggesting that the electrode's conductivity is preserved despite undergoing extensive cycling. SEM

characterizations revealed that stability tests induced slight changes in particle interconnectivity, leading to structural degradation and a reduction in the effective surface area for charge storage. Extended cycling resulted in cracking and particle agglomeration, which increased charge transfer resistance and decreased capacitance. The ex situ XRD tests exposed slight structural changes during charging and discharging, with shifts in peak positions indicating the development of a redox reaction. Verma et al. [101] conducted tests of AC/NiCoSnO₄ electrode resistance variations before and after cycling via charge–discharge processes, utilizing EIS for their assessment. Following 5000 cycles, the EIS curve exhibits a decreased slope, suggesting a reduction in Warburg impedance and enhanced ion diffusion across the electrode. This phenomenon could be attributed to material degradation or phase transformations, which may render the electrode surface less accessible for effective ion transport. Sanchez et al. [131] presented Nyquist plots for the NCMO_rGO hybrid both before and after cycling tests. The analysis revealed negligible variations in overall impedance post-cycling, thereby underscoring the remarkable cycling stability of the composited electrode. Yang et al. [129] performed ex situ XRD and SEM analyses for the ZnCuCoO₄ electrode after 5000 continuous GCD cycles. The SEM analysis conducted following cyclic stability studies demonstrates a uniform coating of the electrode materials, indicating that they remained securely attached to the NF substrate. Besides, the ex situ XRD pattern suggests that the ZnCuCoO₄ electrode maintains its stability on the NF, exhibiting no deformation in its crystal structure throughout the cyclic stability analysis, and no new crystalline phases were identified. The SEM images show that the 2D quasi-nanosheet structure partially transforms into nanospheres or clusters after the cyclic stability test, while some 2D structures remain visible. Teli et al. [132] reported on the structural and morphological changes of the MnVMo-O electrode after 9000 cyclic stability testing. The ex situ XRD analysis revealed the absence of certain diffraction peaks, indicative of structural alterations. Additionally, the SEM images demonstrated modifications in the nanostructures and disintegration of the micro rods. Notably, the EIS measurements revealed significant changes in R_s and R_{ct} , indicating the dissolution of metal ions in the electrolyte during cycling. Overall, there was a decline in initial capacitance attributed to the structural and morphological disruption of the electrode material. Even though TTMOs are an advanced category of materials known for their exceptional properties, including robust and reversible redox transition behavior as well as the ability to form hierarchical heterostructures. However, the development of TTMOs that exhibit strong synergistic effects, ensure mechanical adhesion, and facilitate effective electrical contact presents significant challenges. These challenges stem from the complexities associated with multiple metal compositions and various preparation techniques. In response to these challenges, a range of modifications targeting the structural, morphological, and electronic characteristics has been implemented. These include doping strategies and the development of nanocomposite materials, all aimed at optimizing the performance of TTMO electrodes.

7. Concluding Remarks

7.1. Summary. The rapid expansion of renewable energy systems and PEDs has intensified the demand for advanced energy storage technologies. Central to this progress is the development of high-performance electrode materials. Among them, TTMO nanostructures have emerged as a transformative class, offering significant advantages over binary and single-metal oxides. This report provides a comprehensive overview and perspective on the role of TTMO nanostructures as benchmark electrode materials for energy storage applications, focusing on their synthesis strategies, electrochemical performance, current challenges, and future outlook.

TTMO nanostructures are composed of three distinct metal cations within an oxide matrix. This multi-metal composition introduces a range of oxidation states, which enhances redox activity and enables synergistic interactions among the metal species. These interactions enhance electronic conductivity, improve electrochemical performance, and provide structural flexibility, allowing the engineering of nanostructures with tailored physicochemical properties. Compared to their binary counterparts, TTMOs exhibit higher specific capacitance and energy density, superior cycling stability and rate capability, and greater resilience to structural changes during charge–discharge cycles.

Numerous synthesis techniques have been developed to precisely control the composition, shape, and crystalline phase of TTMOs. Hydrothermal and solvothermal methods, for example, enable the formation of various nanostructures, including nanoneedles, nanosheets, and porous microspheres. Co-precipitation and sol–gel processes allow the even distribution of metal cations, providing fine control over particle size and porosity. Electrochemical deposition supports the creation of nanostructured films on conductive substrates, with morphology modulated by the use of surfactants and additives. The electrochemical characteristics of TTMOs are significantly influenced by their morphology. Nanosheets and nanoneedles, with their large surface areas, facilitate rapid ion movement. Porous microspheres, on the other hand, enhance electrolyte access and improve charge transfer efficiency. Hybrid composites combining TTMOs with carbon materials further boost electrical conductivity while maintaining structural stability. These materials exhibit remarkable efficacy as SC electrodes, with high specific capacitance and outstanding cycling stability. Notably, retention rates exceeding 90% after 1000 cycles are commonly observed, owing to the combined effects of the metal constituents and the stability provided by nanostructuring. TTMOs also demonstrate exceptional rate capability, supporting rapid charge/discharge cycles through efficient electron and ion transport. Studies of the charge storage mechanism in TTMOs suggest that the presence of multiple metal centers offers numerous sites for reversible redox reactions, making them ideal for both capacitive and BT energy storage. The integration of different metals improves electron mobility and structural durability, reducing capacity degradation. Additionally, the porous and nanostructured morphologies increase the active surface area, enabling faster ion transport, which

directly enhances electrochemical performance, particularly in terms of energy density and voltage stability.

7.2. Challenges and Future Directions. Although TTMOs offer considerable potential, several challenges must be addressed. One major limitation is their intrinsic electrical conductivity, which often falls short of the required levels for high-rate applications, necessitating the incorporation of conductive additives to enhance performance. Additionally, certain TTMO compositions may undergo phase changes or dissolution during cycling, resulting in performance degradation over time. The complexity of the synthesis methods and the need for precise control over composition and morphology in TTMO nanostructures also pose challenges for large-scale production. To overcome these issues, several strategies have been explored. The incorporation of graphene or carbon NTs enhances both conductivity and mechanical strength, while the introduction of heteroatoms or the creation of oxygen vacancies can improve redox activity and conductivity. Moreover, advanced synthesis techniques such as solid-state chemistry and surfactant-assisted growth offer innovative approaches for better control over phase stability and morphology, which are crucial for optimizing the performance of TTMOs.

The ability to customize the composition and structure of ternary TTMOs presents significant opportunities for optimizing them for specific applications. By tailoring electrode materials for SCs, hybrid devices, or batteries based on key criteria—such as energy density and power density—nanostructured TTMO-based SCs can be integrated with flexible substrates and textile electronics, thereby expanding their range of potential applications. Due to their exceptional performance characteristics, TTMO nanostructures are increasingly seen as benchmarks for future electrode materials. They demonstrate high capacitance, stability, and rate capability, setting new standards for energy storage technologies. As such, TTMOs serve as reference materials for future research and industrial development, guiding the direction of both academic studies and commercial applications.

TMOs, such as MnO_2 , Co_3O_4 , and NiO , among others, are generally considered to have low toxicity and are more environmentally benign compared to their noble metal oxide counterparts, such as RuO_2 and IrO_2 . The use of base TMOs presents a lower environmental risk due to their abundance and reduced ecological impact during mining and manufacturing processes. Additionally, the ability of these materials to undergo multiple cycles of charge and discharge with minimal environmental degradation contributes to their overall sustainability. The life-cycle aspects of TTMOs are enhanced by their high specific capacitance and energy density, achieved through reversible redox reactions. This makes them suitable for long-life applications in SCs, allowing for prolonged use without frequent replacement, thereby reducing waste. Despite their numerous benefits, recycling and disposal of these materials pose challenges due to the complexity of their compositions and the intricate nanostructures used to optimize performance. The development of efficient recycling processes that do not compromise performance and pose minimal environmental risks remains a key area of ongoing research. Exploring hybrid composites, such as combining TTMOs with carbon materials or

conducting polymers, is one approach to overcoming these challenges while enhancing performance metrics, including conductivity and specific capacitance.

The future direction should focus on surpassing current benchmarks by achieving specific energy densities above 100 Wh kg^{-1} leading to 25% increase in energy density for demonstration at industrial level cells. Power density targets could be above 1000 W kg^{-1} while ensuring the abundance, cost, scalability, and environmental aspects of innovative materials to be used in SC cells. Efforts should focus on increasing cycle numbers to ensure durability, with targets exceeding tens of thousands of cycles without significant capacity loss, making TTMOs more viable for long-term applications. Creating cost-efficient and sustainable methods for the mass production of ternary TTMOs, coupled with a deeper mechanistic understanding of the relationship between composition, structure, and performance, will be crucial for advancing next-generation materials. The focus should be on developing reproducible synthesis methods that maintain consistent quality and performance, which is crucial for scaling up production. Techniques such as electrochemical deposition and physical vapor deposition might offer precise control over material formation and reproducibility. It should also be emphasized that designing environmentally friendly processes to minimize/avoid the use/release of toxic byproducts during synthesis and disposal of TTMOs is crucial even at low technology readiness level (lab scale development). This involves using materials and methods that meet stricter environmental regulations. Innovative approaches to facilitate integration of TTMOs with graphene and their derivatives, conducting polymers, or carbonaceous materials to achieve superior electrochemical performance and stability need to be pursued. Advanced nanostructuring techniques to develop TTMOs with enhanced surface area and ion diffusion capabilities, which could improve both capacitance and scalability should be developed in the near to mid-term. It is also crucial to ensure that new materials and composites align with industry standards for SC applications in diverse sectors, from consumer electronics to automotive applications. A focused effort should be directed at developing thin-coated TTMO electrodes ($<20 \mu\text{m}$) to improve both power and energy density. Last but not the least, to bridge the gap between lab-scale performance and real-world applications in SCs, batteries, and hybrid systems, the research community must realistically work on optimizing synthesis techniques and enhancing scalability aspects of innovative materials with promising performance. Degradation mechanism to unravel the root cause of material/electrode failure will be very useful for designing of next generation TTMO materials. In summary, TTMO nanostructures are revolutionizing electrode material for energy storage, thanks to their unique combination of tunable composition, enhanced redox activity, and structural durability. While challenges remain in terms of conductivity, stability, and scalability, advancements in synthesis methods and material engineering, aided by “AI + X” tools, offer promising avenues for addressing these issues. As benchmarks for future electrode materials, TTMOs are poised to play a central role in advancing high-performance, durable, and adaptable energy storage technologies.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Disclosure

All the authors take full responsibility for the content of this review and approved its submission.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

Periyasamy Sivakumar: writing – original draft, validation, investigation, methodology, data curation, formal analysis, conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Palaniappan Subramanian:** validation, investigation, formal analysis, methodology, conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Palanisamy Kannan:** formal analysis, data curation, validation, conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Jan Minar:** validation, Visualization, writing – review and editing. **Hyun Jung:** writing – review and editing, project administration, resources, funding acquisition, conceptualization.

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